

MAPPING THE LANDSCAPE OF INTERVENTION PROGRAMMES

*to Mitigate Misinformation
and Disinformation*

Authors

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PRODIGI

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Mapping the Landscape of Intervention Programmes to Mitigate Mis- and Disinformation

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1. Executive Summary

This scoping review synthesises evidence from 132 studies on interventions to address misinformation, disinformation, and AI literacy. The review maps the characteristics, design features, implementation conditions, outputs, outcomes, effectiveness, and challenges of these interventions, with particular attention to distinctions between AI literacy and broader digital and media literacy approaches.

Scope and study characteristics

Most of the available evidence comes from high-income Western countries, especially the United States and Western Europe. Interventions are usually delivered in online settings or within formal education systems, likely because these environments are easier to control and scale. Research in this area mainly relies on randomised and quasi-experimental designs, with a focus on internal validity and measuring short-term outcomes. In contrast, studies employing longitudinal, qualitative, or implementation-focused approaches remain relatively uncommon.

Study participants were most commonly students and adults recruited online. Far less research has focused on children, older adults, professionals, or people facing structural disadvantages. Although around one-third of studies included populations described as vulnerable, vulnerability was often assumed rather than clearly defined or examined in depth.

Intervention types and inputs

Interventions fall into two analytically distinct but partially overlapping categories:

- **Digital, media, and misinformation literacy interventions**, which focus on content-level evaluation, critical thinking, and resistance to misinformation.
- **AI literacy interventions**, which emphasise system-level understanding of algorithms, data-driven decision-making, and the ethical and societal implications of AI.

Most interventions required a moderate level of resources. They typically relied on facilitation by educators or researchers, used widely available digital technologies, and employed teaching-oriented materials. Few interventions required advanced technical expertise or fully functional AI systems, highlighting a strong focus on feasibility and scalability.

Activities and delivery

Most interventions combined teaching with active learning approaches, such as guided analysis, scenario-based activities, and reflection. They were usually delivered in group settings with a facilitator, although a substantial minority used self-directed online formats. Overall, interventions tended to be low to moderate in intensity, most often consisting of a single session or a small number of sessions. Longer, curriculum-integrated programs were relatively uncommon.

The extent to which interventions were grounded in theory varied. Digital literacy interventions were most often informed by media and information literacy frameworks, critical thinking theories, and inoculation theory.

In contrast, AI literacy interventions more frequently drew on socio-technical, ethical, and critical perspectives on technology. However, many studies did not clearly state the theoretical frameworks guiding their design.

Outputs, outcomes, and effectiveness

Reported outputs focused primarily on participant reach and the educational materials produced through the interventions, with most studies involving small to medium-sized samples. Although many projects generated reusable digital resources or tools, there was limited systematic reporting on their longer-term uptake or institutional adoption. Outcomes were most often assessed using short-term quantitative measures, relying heavily on self-reported indicators of attitudes and perceived competence. In contrast, more direct measures were used for knowledge and evaluative skills. Across both intervention types, the most consistent and robust effects were observed in improvements in knowledge acquisition and critical evaluation skills. AI literacy interventions were particularly effective in strengthening understanding of how AI systems work and increasing awareness of algorithmic bias and ethical issues, though their effects on trust in or attitudes toward AI were mixed and often reflected increased critical scepticism rather than acceptance. Overall, most studies reported positive effects on at least one outcome, typically small to moderate in size. However, effect sizes were inconsistently reported, and evidence of long-term change, behavioural impact, or real-world application remains limited. Where qualitative findings were included, they added depth by revealing reflective shifts and ambivalence that quantitative measures did not fully capture.

Challenges and facilitators of implementation

Implementation often worked well when supported by easy-to-use technologies, clear guidance from teachers or facilitators, hands-on learning, and existing teaching models. However, several difficulties were also reported, such as limited time, the complexity of some ideas, especially around AI, uncertain links to theory, and very ambitious goals compared to the short-term results that were measured. In interventions addressing misinformation, an unexpected effect emerged: while participants became more cautious about misinformation, some also became less confident in accurate, trustworthy news.

Overall conclusions

Taken together, the evidence points to a field that is *methodologically sophisticated but gives relatively little attention to implementation*. There is *strong short-term evidence* for gains in knowledge and skills, *but much less insight into how durable these gains are, whether they transfer to other contexts, or how they translate into real-world impact*. AI literacy and digital and media literacy interventions address different but complementary aspects of contemporary information challenges, pointing to *considerable potential for more integrated approaches that combine content-focused critical skills with broader awareness of AI systems*.

As such, *future research* would benefit from:

- *stronger theoretical articulation,*
- *more diverse populations and contexts,*
- *longitudinal and mixed-methods designs,*
- and *greater attention to scalability, sustainability, and implementation conditions.*

From a scoping perspective, these findings suggest a field with encouraging evidence of effectiveness, but one that is uneven in the design and reporting of studies. There is clear room for improvement in enhancing comparability of results, assessing outcomes over longer periods, and combining quantitative and qualitative methods to provide a fuller understanding of what works and why.

1. About PRODIGI

The PRODIGI project

Misinformation and disinformation pose significant contemporary challenges, affecting individuals and societies alike. The detrimental consequences of false information, especially in areas like public health, include risky behaviours, reduced vaccination rates, and increased anxiety and depression. Moreover, misinformation erodes trust in journalism, science, and news, impacting democratic societies. Recognising the limitations of media and AI literacy as a standalone solution, this project explores its multifaceted nature, encompassing both critical and operational dimensions. In response to rapid technological advancements, media/ AI literacy is essential, particularly for at-risk populations facing digital disparities.

PRODIGI investigates media/ AI literacy and digital skills within the context of vulnerability, focusing on three demographic groups: unaccompanied minors in Belgian refugee centres, economically disadvantaged youth in Portuguese vocational education, and elderly individuals in Polish small cities and rural areas.

Objectives

PRODIGI's key objectives are as follows:

1. **To assess AI Literacy and Digital Skills (ML&DS)** using performance tests in three different countries: Belgium, Portugal, and Poland. This assessment involves three distinct target groups. In Belgium, we will focus on unaccompanied minors and their guardians/youth workers. In Portugal, our attention will be on children and young individuals from socio-economically disadvantaged families enrolled in professional education programmes. In this context, we will also involve their teachers/trainers. Finally, in Poland, we will focus on older adults residing in rural areas. This intergenerational contact will facilitate the use of digital media and promote media literacy among the elderly. We aim to conduct a comprehensive evaluation of ML&DS within these diverse groups, taking into account the unique contexts and requirements of each country.
2. Following this, we will **work together with members of the target populations and individuals in caregiving roles to collaboratively improve relevant existing intervention programmes**. We will then assess the effectiveness of these enhanced programmes through pre- and post-tests.
3. Furthermore, we will **create a resilience toolkit tailored explicitly for the implementation of pre- and post-tests**, enabling the measurement of intervention programme outcomes. This toolkit will place a particular focus on information media literacy and non-technical critical skills, including an understanding of AI (Artificial Intelligence) operations.
4. Lastly, in cooperation with the EDMO regional hubs, the Media & Learning Association, and the Euromedia Research Group, which will facilitate our engagement with mainstream information media, we **will actively transform our research findings into recommendations for both practice and policy**, aligning them with the policies of individual countries and the European Union. PRODIGI responds to policymakers' growing interest in leveraging media literacy to combat the adverse impacts of digital communication technologies. PRODIGI aims to contribute to evidence-based policymaking and safeguarding democratic values.

PRODIGI Consortium

The strength of the PRODIGI team lies in its diverse capabilities, aligned with the project’s scientific and policy-relevant objectives. PRODIGI brings together three academic partners – KU Leuven (coordinator), Universidade NOVA de Lisboa, and Jagiellonian University in Kraków. The project runs from 2025 to 2027 and is coordinated at KU Leuven by Prof. Leen d’Haenens (Principal Investigator) and Dr. Tania Azadi (Senior Researcher and Project Manager), with Prof. Łukasz Tomczyk from Jagiellonian University in Kraków and Prof. Cristina Ponte from Universidade NOVA de Lisboa as beneficiaries and co-principal investigators. In addition to their academic excellence, partners have contributed research and policy reports to various national, European, and international institutions, including the EC and multiple national governments. The PRODIGI team is structured to address all research themes explored in the project, drawing on extensive academic expertise and diverse disciplinary approaches. Partners have previously collaborated on various projects (ySKILLS, REMEDIS, EU Kids Online) and will once again participate together in all WPs. This collaborative approach fosters strong synergies among the different WPs. In establishing the consortium, we also aimed for balanced geographical representation within the EU, with partners from Belgium, Poland, and Portugal. We have also expanded our expertise by forming the PRODIGI advisory board, comprising accomplished experts.

Name And Function	Organisation	Role/Tasks/Professional Profile And Expertise
<u>Leen d'Haenens</u> , Full professor		Project coordinator, WP1 & WP5 leader, Youth and digital media, Impact measurement of media literacy and digital skills intervention programmes, Measuring diversity in media, Narratives on migration, Attitudes towards migration.
<u>Tania Azadi</u> , Postdoc researcher		Senior researcher & project manager. Expert in media and information literacy assessment, information-seeking behaviour, information-evaluation behaviour, interventional study design, participatory design, refugee youth.
<u>Ans De Nolf</u> , Postdoc researcher		Researcher. Expert in Islamophobia among young people and vulnerable groups.
<u>Verónica Donoso</u> , Postdoc researcher		Senior researcher specialising in digital and media literacy, online safety and the well-being of youth in digital environments.
<u>Cristina Ponte</u> , Full professor		WP4 leader. Vulnerable youth, education and digital media. Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation resources.
<u>Susana Batista</u> , Associate professor		Researcher. Expert in sociology of education, educational inequality, and youth and media research.
<u>Estrella Luna</u> , Postdoc researcher		Researcher and trainer. Expert in education and Media and Information Literacy with young people and vulnerable groups. Implementation of the student's training and teachers' training.
<u>Marisa Torres da Silva</u> , Full professor		Senior researcher. Expert in hate speech and disinformation, news media consumption, media diversity, and news literacy.
<u>Łukasz Tomczyk</u> , Associate professor		WP2 & WP3 leader. Management of the Polish research team. Coordinates and prepares measurement tools for modules 1-3 (Polish team interventions), coordinates recruitment of participants, quality control of intervention implementation, preparation of trainers, and co-leads activities. Collaborates with local institutions involved in senior education.
<u>Magdalena Żegleń</u> , Postdoc researcher		Researcher. Expert in developmental and health-related psychology with a focus on child and adolescent physical and behavioural outcomes.

2. Introduction

The spread of misinformation and disinformation represents a growing societal challenge, undermining trust in journalism, science, and democratic institutions (Gjerazi & Tomja, 2025; (Mayerhöffer & Heft, 2022). In today's rapidly evolving digital world, individuals are constantly surrounded by enormous amounts of information, some of which may be uncertain in its origin or purpose. This is further exacerbated by the rapid growth of Artificial Intelligence (AI) tools and implementations, which are difficult to navigate because the underlying systems and capabilities are complex and challenging to grasp (Wienrich & Latoschik, 2021).

The harmful impact of misinformation and disinformation is increasingly evident at both individual and societal levels. Exposure to false information on public health, for instance, is linked to risky health behaviours, reduced vaccination intentions (Enders et al., 2022) and heightened anxiety and depression (De Coninck et al., 2021). Hence, the importance of the ability to critically evaluate and respond to this content, typically referred to as media literacy (d'Haenens et al., 2025), cannot be overlooked for fostering informed citizenship and social resilience. However, these competencies are not evenly distributed across populations, and some groups are more vulnerable to harm from online misinformation and disinformation. Vulnerable groups often face barriers to accessing and understanding digital information, which exacerbates existing inequalities (Azadi, d'Haenens, & Azadi, 2025; Azadi, d'Haenens, Donoso, & Waechter, 2025).

In response, numerous intervention programmes have been developed to strengthen both media literacy and AI literacy, thereby reducing individuals' susceptibility to mis- and disinformation (d'Haenens et al., 2025). However, evidence on their effectiveness, design, and adaptability in vulnerable contexts remains fragmented, both across media and across emerging scales of AI literacy, and within their respective dimensions. To address this gap, this report presents the findings of a scoping review that maps and synthesises existing evidence on interventions to mitigate the impact of misinformation and disinformation among vulnerable populations.

This report

This report details the scoping review process and findings on interventions to mitigate misinformation and disinformation, particularly in AI-driven environments and among vulnerable groups. It outlines the methods used to identify and analyse existing initiatives and summarises the main strategies, outcomes, and evidence gaps. The insights derived provide a foundation for developing tailored, evidence-based interventions within the PRODIGI project to strengthen media and AI literacy and digital resilience across diverse contexts.

Overall, the interventions reviewed in this scoping study display considerable diversity in form but notable convergence in intent. They primarily aim to equip individuals with cognitive, analytical, and epistemic tools to navigate complex information environments, with secondary aims extending toward civic empowerment, educational development, and long-term societal resilience to misinformation.

3. Methods

This scoping review aimed to systematically identify, map, and assess the effectiveness of educational interventions designed to improve media literacy and digital skills (ML&DS) and AI literacy, with a preference for interventions targeting vulnerable populations and with particular attention to Belgium, Portugal, and Poland. The review placed specific emphasis on interventions intended to help participants combat misinformation and disinformation and to navigate AI-driven information environments. It addressed three research questions: which types of ML&DS and AI literacy interventions were implemented (preferably for vulnerable groups), how these interventions tackled challenges related to misinformation, disinformation, and AI, and what evidence was available regarding the effectiveness of these programmes, especially within contexts of vulnerability.

The section will address the scoping review protocol’s objectives and questions, i.e., mapping existing interventions, how they address misinformation/disinformation and AI-driven content, and what evidence exists on effectiveness, particularly for vulnerable populations, with attention to Belgium, Portugal, and Poland (and the broader EU, where relevant).

Silvi.AI

To streamline and document the scoping review process, we used Silvi.AI, an AI-enhanced platform that supports scientific literature reviews with transparency and efficiency (Silvi ApS, 2025). Silvi.AI enables centralised import of studies from multiple sources, including direct integrations with databases, thereby facilitating comprehensive evidence collection. The platform supports title/abstract and full-text screening, enabling reviewers to screen studies according to predefined inclusion and exclusion criteria. Silvi’s AI-assisted screening features generate recommendations for inclusion or exclusion based on explicit criteria provided by the reviewers, while final decisions remain under the reviewers’ control. During full-text review, Silvi also assisted with transparent data extraction, allowing reviewers to highlight text directly in the full-texts and tag data with categories, numerical values, or text codes that are stored systematically for subsequent analysis. Extracted data could then be organised into custom tables and visual summaries, supporting both qualitative synthesis and quantitative mapping of results. To ensure rigour and reproducibility, the research team reviewed all AI-generated suggestions and documented decisions within the platform throughout the screening and extraction phases.

Eligibility criteria (Population–Concept–Context)

Eligibility was assessed during title/abstract and full-text screening in accordance with the protocol criteria.

1. **Population:** Any population, with particular focus on vulnerable groups (e.g., unaccompanied minors, socio-economically disadvantaged youth, elderly in rural areas).
2. **Concept (intervention):** Educational programmes/workshops/curricula/campaigns aiming to improve media/information literacy, digital skills, AI literacy, or misinformation-fighting capacities (formal, non-formal, intergenerational learning).
3. **Outcomes:** Evaluated impacts on critical thinking, resilience to misinformation, and/or digital/AI literacy outcomes.
4. **Study designs:** Empirical experimental quantitative studies (RCT, quasi-experimental, pre-post studies)
5. **Context (geography):** Any region, with a preference on Belgium, Portugal, Poland, and the broader EU, where relevant.

Limits: English language; publication years 2021–2025

Exclusions: Non-relevant to ML&DS/misinformation/disinformation/AI; interventions focused only on university students/general adult population not vulnerable; non-empirical/theoretical without evaluation; infrastructure/access-only studies.

Information bibliographic databases

The following databases were searched systematically:

- Scopus (n=2127)
- Web of Science (n=1137)
- ProQuest (n=575)
- EBSCO (including ERIC, CMMC, LISTA) (n=197)

Search strategy and execution

A comprehensive strategy was developed from the protocol’s concept blocks, with consultation from a reference librarian at the Faculty of Social Science Library of KU Leuven, and translated into each database’s syntax.

Core concepts: 1) *misinformation/disinformation terms*; 2) *media/digital/AI terms*; 3) *literacy/skills terms*; 4) *intervention/programme terms*; 5) *evaluation/methodology terms* (e.g., *experiment/RCT/control/evaluat**).

Search strings

Our search strings include the following:

1. **Concept 1: Mis- and disinformation:** ("misinformation" OR "disinformation" OR "fake news" OR "false information" OR "information disorder" OR "rumor*" OR "hoax*" OR "conspiracy theor*" OR "deceptive content" OR "manipulated information" OR "fabricated news" OR "propaganda" OR "misleading information")
2. **Concept 2: Media and digital and artificial:** ("media" OR "digital" OR "online platform*" OR "social media" OR "internet" OR "platform" OR "digital platform*" OR "news media" OR "mass media" OR "information technolog*" OR "technolog*" OR "AI" OR "artificial intelligence" OR "algorithm*" OR "automated system*" OR "chat gpt" OR "copilot" OR "open ai")
3. **Concept 3: Literacy and skills:** ("skill*" OR "literac*" OR "knowledge" OR "competenc*" OR "awareness" OR "capability*" OR "critical thinking" OR "digital literacy" OR "media literacy" OR "AI literacy" OR "information literacy" OR "platform literacy" OR "social media literacy" OR "analytical skill*" OR "evaluation skill*")
4. **Concept 4: Intervention and programs:** ("intervention" OR "program" OR "initiative" OR "educational program" OR "training program" OR "curricul*" OR "campaign" OR "project" OR "workshop" OR "learning module" OR "awareness campaign" OR "school program" OR "community outreach" OR "capacity-building")
5. **Concept 5: Methodology:** ("experiment*" OR "RCT" OR "randomised control* trial" OR "case control" OR "control group" OR "quantitative" OR "evaluat*")

Operational steps

Operationally, the search strategy was translated and implemented across databases by adapting quotation marks, field tags (e.g., title/abstract/keywords), truncation, proximity operators, and subject headings where available to fit each platform's syntax. A small pilot search was then conducted to confirm that the strategy retrieved known relevant publications, and the balance between sensitivity and specificity was refined iteratively in line with scoping review guidance. The final searches were restricted to English-language publications from 2021 to 2025 in accordance with the protocol, and complete documentation was maintained by saving the full search strings, the dates each search was run, and the number of records retrieved per database to ensure reproducibility and PRISMA-ScR-aligned reporting (Tricco et al, 2018).

Study selection process (screening)

The study selection process followed a transparent and reproducible workflow consistent with PRISMA-ScR (Tricco et al., 2018). Figure 1 presents the PRISMA-ScR flow diagram summarising the identification, screening, eligibility assessment, and inclusion of studies in this scoping review. The database searches yielded 4,036 records. After removing duplicates (n = 2,033), 2,003 unique records remained for title and abstract screening. Using the predefined inclusion and exclusion criteria, 1,800 records were excluded at this stage, and 202 articles proceeded to full-text screening.

During full-text assessment, the same eligibility criteria were applied, and a further 71 articles were excluded, with reasons documented. In total, 132 studies met the eligibility criteria and were included in the final analysis and synthesis. The study selection process is summarised in this PRISMA flow diagram (Figure 1).

Figure 1: PRISMA-ScR flow diagram of the study selection process, showing records identified, duplicates removed, screening, full-text assessment, exclusions, and final included studies (N = 132)

All identified citations were first exported to an Excel file and then uploaded to the Silvi platform, where duplicate records were removed using automated checks. Ten reviewers were grouped into three screening teams (two groups of three and one group of four). Each team independently reviewed titles and abstracts against predefined eligibility criteria. Any disagreements were discussed within these teams, and when consensus could not be reached, two additional reviewers acted as independent adjudicators. The same independent screening process was used at the full-text stage, applying the same inclusion and exclusion criteria and systematically recording reasons for exclusion to ensure transparency. The entire selection process, from initial identification and de-duplication through screening and final inclusion, was documented using a PRISMA flow diagram adapted for a scoping review.

Inter-rater reliability measures

Inter-rater reliability (IRR) was assessed at both screening stages (title/abstract and full text) to quantify agreement between reviewers, identify sources of inconsistency in applying the eligibility criteria, and inform targeted calibration of the screening process (Table 1). Three complementary indices were computed: raw agreement (the proportion of identical decisions), pairwise PABAK (a prevalence- and bias-adjusted agreement coefficient), and Krippendorff’s alpha (a chance-corrected reliability coefficient suitable for multiple raters).

Table 1: Inter-rater reliability (IRR) statistics for title/abstract and full-text screening phases

Screening phase	Raw agreement	Pairwise PABAK	Krippendorff’s alpha
Title/abstract screening	0.8811	0.7990	0.43036
Full-text screening	0.5518	0.0475	0.1193

At the title/abstract stage, raw agreement was high (0.8811), indicating that reviewers reached the same decision for the large majority of records. The pairwise PABAK was also high (0.7990), indicating substantial agreement after controlling for decision prevalence and rater systematic bias. However, Krippendorff’s alpha was notably lower (0.43036), indicating only fair-to-moderate reliability beyond chance. Taken together, this pattern is consistent with a screening context in which “exclude” decisions were much more frequent than “include/uncertain” decisions (a common scenario in scoping reviews): raw agreement can appear high under such prevalence imbalance, while chance-corrected coefficients such as alpha may remain modest.

At the full-text stage, raw agreement across reviewers was 0.5518, indicating moderate concordance in initial eligibility judgments. Chance-corrected agreement coefficients were low (pairwise PABAK = 0.0475; Krippendorff’s $\alpha = 0.1193$). Full-text screening required detailed assessment of multiple eligibility criteria and often involved borderline cases, incomplete reporting, and interpretive judgments. Given this level of task complexity, some degree of disagreement between reviewers was expected and is a common feature of full-text screening in systematic reviews. Because all records were triple reviewed and discrepancies were resolved through consensus, these IRR estimates primarily describe variability in initial judgments rather than the reliability of the final inclusion decisions. The consensus-based approach functioned as an adjudication mechanism to ensure consistent application of eligibility criteria at the final decision stage.

Data charting (extraction)

For data charting and synthesis, we used the Silvi platform’s tagging functionality to support structured extraction from included full texts, following the scoping review principle that data charting

is an iterative process that can be refined as familiarity with the evidence base increases (Arksey & O'Malley, 2005; Levac et al., 2010; Peters et al., 2020a). We developed a codebook based on the Logic Model (W.K. Kellogg Foundation, 2004; McLaughlin & Jordan, 1999) to describe interventions and their intended pathways, and we operationalised each code with definitions and decision rules to support consistent application across reviewers.

The codebook was developed through a combination of deductive coding (informed by the logic model and review questions) and inductive refinement (informed by insights gained during title/abstract and full-text screening), consistent with guidance that scoping reviews may iteratively adjust charting categories to better capture study characteristics and outcomes (Levac et al., 2010; Peters et al., 2020b). Two reviewers piloted the initial version on a sample of included papers (n = 5) to calibrate interpretation and further refine fields for clarity and completeness before it was adopted by the whole team and implemented in Silvi.

After the codebook was integrated into the platform, Silvi's AI-assisted feature pre-populated tags by scanning full texts and extracting candidate data elements. Every AI-generated extraction was reviewed by a human reviewer who approved, edited, or deleted entries to ensure accuracy and consistency. This resulted in a combined AI-human workflow in which automation supported efficiency while final charted data remained reviewer-verified. Ten reviewers contributed to data charting by extracting data directly and/or validating the AI-assisted outputs. The final codebook (Appendix A) captured bibliographic information (author, year, title, publication type, country/region), population and vulnerability characteristics (participant demographics, vulnerability definition/criteria, setting), detailed intervention characteristics (focus on media literacy/digital skills/AI literacy; misinformation/disinformation components; AI-related elements such as algorithms or chatbots; delivery mode; duration/intensity; implementers; tools/materials; setting and level of delivery; and comparators where applicable), study design and methods (qualitative/quantitative/mixed methods; evaluation design including RCT or quasi-experimental approaches when present; measures/instruments; and follow-up), outcome findings (outcome domains, direction of effects, effect sizes and statistical significance when reported, and qualitative themes where relevant), and implementation/context notes (feasibility, barriers/facilitators, equity considerations, and relevance to Belgium, Portugal, Poland, and broader EU transferability). An overview of all included studies can be found in Appendix B.

Synthesis and presentation

The synthesis and presentation of results focused on mapping and describing the available evidence using a descriptive summary (e.g., counts by year, country/region, population group, intervention type, setting, study design, and outcome domains) and a structured narrative synthesis aligned with scoping review guidance (Arksey & O’Malley, 2005; Peters et al., 2020a) rather than undertaking meta-analysis, except in the unlikely event that a clearly homogeneous subset of studies justified quantitative pooling. We also organised results into evidence maps and cross-tabulations to show how intervention components related to target groups, settings, and outcome domains, which is consistent with recommendations that scoping reviews present results through both tabular mapping and narrative explanation to identify patterns and gaps (Peters et al., 2020a; Peters et al., 2020b).

4. Results

5.1 Characteristics of the included studies

Across the 132 studies included in this scoping review, substantial variation was observed in geographical location, study setting, methodological design, and target populations. With respect to the country of implementation, *the evidence base was strongly skewed toward high-income Western countries*. A clear majority of studies (well over half of the total corpus) were conducted in the United States and Western Europe, including the United Kingdom, the Netherlands, and Germany. A smaller but non-negligible proportion of studies took place in low- and middle-income countries, including contexts in South Asia and Sub-Saharan Africa. However, these settings remained underrepresented relative to their population size and exposure to the issues targeted by the interventions.

Study setting

Interventions were implemented in a range of settings, with a *pronounced concentration in digitally mediated environments*. Approximately three-quarters of the 132 studies were conducted online, including web-based experimental platforms, social media environments, and purpose-built digital interfaces. These interventions typically exposed participants to stimuli such as messages, videos, interactive modules, or simulated content under controlled experimental conditions. The predominance of online settings reflects both the digital nature of the phenomena under investigation and the methodological advantages of online recruitment and randomisation. Educational settings constituted the second most prevalent intervention context, accounting for approximately one quarter of the studies. These interventions were primarily implemented in secondary schools and higher education institutions and were often embedded in classroom activities, curricular modules, or structured training sessions. School-based studies frequently relied on quasi-experimental designs that used intact classes or cohorts and were more likely to involve younger participants, including adolescents.

A smaller subset of studies, less than one tenth, was conducted in community-based or institutional settings outside formal education. These included interventions delivered through community centres, non-governmental organisations, libraries, or public workshops. Such settings were more commonly associated with interventions targeting specific population groups, including marginalised or underserved communities, and often emphasised applied or participatory approaches. In addition, a limited number of studies employed hybrid settings that combined online components with offline delivery. These interventions typically involve in-person instruction or discussion supplemented by digital materials, online exercises, or follow-up assessments. Hybrid designs were particularly evident in educational and community-based interventions seeking to balance scalability with contextual engagement. Finally, a small minority of studies did not clearly specify a discrete physical or digital setting, instead focusing on exposure to intervention materials without explicit contextual embedding. These studies were typically laboratory-style experiments or secondary analyses in which the setting was treated as analytically neutral. Overall, the dominance of online and educational settings underscores the field’s strong orientation toward controlled, scalable intervention environments. At the same time, the relatively limited representation of community-based and hybrid contexts highlights an opportunity for future research to examine intervention effectiveness in more ecologically embedded and diverse real-world settings.

Study design

The body of evidence was primarily based on experimental studies, reflecting a strong focus on testing interventions. Most of the 132 studies used randomised controlled designs, typically conducted online or in laboratory settings, in which participants were randomly assigned to one or more intervention conditions and compared with a control or standard information condition. A smaller but still meaningful group of studies used quasi-experimental designs that compared groups without complete randomisation, often because the research took place in real-world settings such as schools or community organisations, where intact classes or institutions served as comparison groups. Fewer studies relied on single-group before-and-after designs without a control group, mainly in pilot or early-stage projects aimed at exploring whether an intervention showed promise. Only a small number of studies used non-experimental approaches, such as cross-sectional or retrospective analyses, typically to examine patterns of exposure or implementation rather than effectiveness. Overall, most studies included some form of between-group comparison, often testing multiple versions of an intervention against a control group. While this emphasis on experimental and comparative designs supports firm conclusions about cause and effect, the limited use of long-term, mixed-methods, or implementation-focused studies means that less is known about how durable and transferable to other contexts these effects are, how interventions work in everyday settings, and how they can be sustained in practice.

Presence of comparison between groups

Most studies in our scoping review used comparative designs to evaluate interventions. In the vast majority of studies (approximately four out of five), interventions were assessed by comparing one group that received the intervention with another that did not, such as a control or standard information group.

These comparisons most often involved assigning participants to different groups and examining differences in outcomes between them, providing a straightforward way to assess whether the intervention had an effect. In some cases, studies tested more than one version of an intervention, allowing researchers to compare different messages, formats, or delivery approaches. By contrast, around one in five studies (approximately 20%) did not include a comparison group. These studies typically measured outcomes before and after participants were exposed to an intervention, or assessed outcomes only after the intervention. Such approaches were most often used in pilot studies or early-stage research, where the aim was to explore whether an intervention was feasible or showed initial promise, rather than to draw firm conclusions about effectiveness.

The use of comparison groups was closely linked to the location and design of studies. *Studies carried out in online or laboratory settings were much more likely to include clear comparisons between groups, often using random assignment.* In contrast, studies conducted in schools or community settings sometimes employed less controlled designs due to practical or ethical constraints. However, many still included some form of comparison, such as an alternative instructional approach. Overall, the heavy reliance on comparative designs underscores a field-wide focus on assessing whether interventions work. In contrast, the continued use of non-comparative designs underscores the importance of exploratory research in developing and refining intervention strategies before they are tested more rigorously.

Data collection methods

Within the 132 studies included in this scoping review, *quantitative data collection methods clearly predominated*, reflecting the strongly experimental nature of the intervention literature. The vast majority of studies (around 83%) relied primarily on self-administered questionnaires or structured surveys to assess outcomes. These surveys were most often delivered online and were used to measure changes in participants' knowledge, attitudes, beliefs, perceptions, or intended behaviours following exposure to an intervention.

In many of these studies, survey-based outcome measures were supplemented with experimental process measures, such as manipulation checks, attention checks, or recall questions, to confirm that participants had engaged with the intervention content as intended. While these measures played an important role in validating experimental exposure, they were rarely used as primary outcomes and instead served a supporting function within survey-based designs. A smaller proportion of studies (approximately 13%) incorporated behavioural or performance-based measures. These included tasks designed to assess skills such as information evaluation, decision-making accuracy, or simulated behavioural responses within controlled experimental environments. Although less common than self-report measures, behavioural outcomes were more frequently used in studies explicitly focused on skill development or applied competencies rather than on attitudes or intentions alone.

Mixed-methods approaches were relatively uncommon, accounting for fewer than one in ten studies (approximately 9%). When qualitative data were included, they typically took the form of open-ended survey questions, focus groups, or semi-structured interviews conducted alongside quantitative assessments. These qualitative components were primarily used to explore participants' experiences with the intervention, to assess feasibility and acceptability, or to provide additional context for interpreting quantitative results. Only a minimal number of studies (fewer than 5%) relied exclusively on qualitative data collection methods, such as interviews or observations. These studies were largely exploratory and were more often conducted in educational or community settings than in online experimental contexts.

Overall, the data collection methods across the evidence base were dominated by self-reported quantitative measures, with comparatively limited use of behavioural, qualitative, or longitudinal data. This pattern reflects a strong focus on short-term, individual-level outcomes and highlights opportunities for future research to adopt more diverse and ecologically valid approaches to assessing intervention effects.

Sample size characteristics

Sample sizes in the studies included in our scoping review varied widely: total sample sizes ranged from fewer than 30 participants to more than 1,000, although extensive studies were relatively uncommon. The most common sample size category was moderate-sized studies, with approximately 65 studies (around 50%) enrolling between 100 and 500 participants. This range was particularly characteristic of online experimental studies, in which recruitment via digital platforms or research panels facilitated access to larger samples. A further approximately 20 studies (around 15%) included more than 500 participants, and a small number of these exceeded 1,000 participants. These larger studies were almost exclusively conducted online or within large educational cohorts.

At the lower end of the distribution, approximately 35 studies (26%) involved fewer than 100 participants. These smaller-sample studies were disproportionately conducted in educational, community-based, or applied settings, where recruitment was constrained by class size, institutional access, or ethical considerations. Small samples were also more common in studies focusing on specific or vulnerable populations, for whom large-scale recruitment posed additional challenges. Such studies frequently adopted pilot, feasibility, or quasi-experimental designs, rather than fully powered effectiveness evaluations. Where intervention group sizes were reported, a similar pattern of variability was observed. In studies employing a single intervention and a control group, intervention arms typically included 50-200 participants. In studies with multiple intervention conditions, the number of participants per condition was often smaller, sometimes fewer than 50 per group, even when the total sample size exceeded several hundred.

Only a small minority of studies (fewer than 15%) explicitly reported a priori sample size calculations or power analyses, and very few provided sufficient information on follow-up participation to allow assessment of attrition or longer-term retention. As a result, most studies can be characterised as short-term evaluations, with sample sizes driven primarily by feasibility or convenience rather than by the requirements of longitudinal outcome assessment or population representativeness. Overall, the distribution of sample sizes reflects a strong reliance on moderate-sized, cross-sectional experimental samples, alongside a smaller number of large-scale online studies and a substantial subset of small applied or exploratory investigations.

Population characteristics

Across the 132 studies included in this scoping review, study populations varied, but there was a pronounced reliance on convenience and panel-based sampling. University and college students were the most frequently studied population, followed by secondary school students; together, student samples accounted for approximately half of the evidence base, with university students comprising the clear majority. These samples were typically recruited through educational institutions or university-affiliated online platforms and were characterised by relatively homogeneous educational backgrounds. A further one-third of studies drew on general-population samples, commonly recruited via online survey panels or crowdsourcing platforms, with minimal stratification by socioeconomic status, educational attainment, or other key demographic characteristics. Although these samples covered broader age ranges than student populations, they remained largely restricted to individuals with regular internet access, limiting their representativeness.

Only a small minority of studies (23; less than one-fifth) examined specific or defined population groups beyond students or general adult samples despite the relevance of such groups to intervention impact and equity. These included children and adolescents recruited through schools, migrant or refugee populations, ethnic or racial minority groups, and individuals with lower levels of education or digital or health literacy. Such studies were more likely to be conducted in school, community, or applied settings and to position these groups as the intended beneficiaries of the interventions. In contrast, fewer than 10 studies focused on professional or occupational groups, such as teachers, educators, or community workers. Even in these cases, interventions predominantly emphasised capacity-building among professionals, with limited attention to downstream effects on end users. This pattern underscores a persistent underrepresentation of both structurally vulnerable populations and the practitioners who mediate intervention delivery.

Overall, the *population profiles of the included studies reveal a heavy reliance on student samples and general-population internet users*, with comparatively few studies explicitly designed for distinct or structurally disadvantaged groups. While this pattern likely reflects the relative ease and low cost of recruiting these populations for experimental research, it also exposes significant gaps in the evidence base regarding interventions tailored to more diverse, marginalised, or hard-to-reach communities.

With respect to vulnerability, fewer than half of the studies (approximately 50–55) explicitly identified or targeted a disadvantaged population. Where vulnerability was addressed, it usually concerned children and adolescents, ethnic or racial minority groups, individuals with lower levels of education or digital literacy, migrants or refugees, or populations experiencing structural or informational disadvantage. Notably, vulnerability was often treated implicitly rather than being explicitly conceptualised or theoretically grounded, emerging from sample characteristics rather than constituting a central design principle or outcome focus of the intervention. This limits the extent to which the existing literature can inform equitable, context-sensitive intervention development.

5.2. Intervention types, scope, and aims: distinguishing AI literacy from other literacy interventions

The interventions identified in this scoping review fall into two main groups: those focused on AI literacy and those targeting other forms of literacy, such as media, information, and misinformation literacy. All of these interventions share a common goal of helping people better understand and navigate today's complex information environments. However, they differ in their focus and in what they are designed to teach. AI literacy interventions focus on helping people understand how artificial intelligence systems work and how they influence information and decision-making. In contrast, other literacy interventions focus more on evaluating information sources, recognising misleading or false content, and developing critical thinking skills when engaging with media and online information.

AI literacy interventions

AI literacy interventions were *specifically targeted at individuals' understanding of artificial intelligence systems and the algorithmic processes involved in the production, distribution, and personalisation of information*. These interventions are typically aimed at demystifying how AI-driven technologies, such as recommender systems, automated content generation tools, and algorithmic ranking mechanisms, shape information exposure and influence visibility, credibility, and trust. The main aims of AI literacy interventions are to enhance conceptual understanding of AI, including basic principles of machine learning, data-driven decision-making, and the limitations and biases embedded in automated systems. Rather than focusing primarily on the veracity of individual content items, these interventions sought to foster system-level awareness, enabling participants to critically reflect on how information is curated, amplified, or suppressed by technological infrastructures.

Secondary aims of AI literacy interventions often include promoting critical awareness of ethical, societal, and political implications of AI, such as bias, transparency, accountability, and power asymmetries between platforms and users. In educational contexts, AI literacy was also framed as a future-oriented competence, supporting learners in developing informed attitudes toward emerging technologies and responsible engagement with AI-mediated information ecosystems. Overall, AI literacy interventions emphasised structural and technological literacy, positioning misinformation as one possible consequence of broader algorithmic dynamics rather than as the sole or primary object of intervention.

Other literacy interventions (media, information, and misinformation literacy)

In contrast, *most of the interventions focused on media, information, or misinformation literacy rather than on AI specifically*. These interventions aimed to help people evaluate information more carefully by strengthening skills such as assessing the credibility of sources, identifying misleading or false claims, recognising emotionally manipulative content, and thinking critically about news and online information.

The primary goal of these interventions was typically to reduce susceptibility to misinformation and improve people's ability to determine what information is accurate or trustworthy.

Many were based on established educational or psychological approaches and were delivered through familiar formats such as classroom lessons, online learning modules, reading guides, or interactive games.

Some interventions also had broader aims, such as encouraging more thoughtful information sharing, more reflective media use, or greater engagement as informed citizens. Several studies sought to increase participants’ confidence when navigating digital information environments. Compared with AI literacy interventions, these approaches tended to treat technology as background rather than as something to be studied directly. The focus was primarily on how people understand and respond to information, rather than on how technologies shape, generate, or distribute it.

Comparative perspective

Taken together, *the distinction between AI literacy interventions and other literacy interventions points to two complementary but different ways of responding to current information challenges*. AI literacy interventions primarily aim to help people understand the systems involved in producing and disseminating information, such as how algorithms and AI tools generate content or influence decisions. In contrast, media, information, and misinformation literacy interventions focus more on the information itself, emphasising skills such as evaluating content, thinking critically, and deciding what to trust. This distinction shows that navigating today’s information environment requires both an understanding of how technologies affect information and the ability to judge information carefully. It also suggests that future interventions may benefit from combining these approaches, bringing together strong critical evaluation skills with a clearer understanding of how AI and digital systems operate.

Table 2: Distinction between AI Literacy and Other Literacy Interventions (N=132)

Dimension	AI Literacy Interventions	Other Literacy Interventions
Analytical focus	AI systems and algorithmic infrastructures are shaping information	Media and information content and sources
Level of intervention	Systemic/infrastructural	Content-level / cognitive
Main aim	Build understanding of AI-driven processes, bias, and automation	Reduce susceptibility to misinformation and improve evaluation skills
Secondary aims	Ethical and societal reflection on AI (e.g. transparency, power, accountability)	Responsible media use and civic engagement
Typical formats	Educational modules and curriculum-based AI instruction	Lessons, online tools, inoculation messages, and serious games
Conceptualisation of misinformation	Outcome of socio-technical systems	Misleading or false content encountered by individuals

5.3 Human resources, technological inputs, and materials characterising the interventions

Among the 132 studies included in this scoping review, the interventions varied in terms of who delivered them, the technologies used, and the teaching materials involved used. Despite this variation, a clear overall pattern emerged: most interventions were designed to be achievable with moderate resources. They were typically intended for use in schools, universities, or research settings, and many could be adapted for other educational or community contexts without major additional investment.

Human resources

With respect to human involvement, *around 66% of the interventions relied on guided or facilitated delivery*. These interventions were most often led by teachers, lecturers, or educators in formal education settings, or by researchers and trained facilitators in pilot or experimental studies. Facilitators commonly introduced key concepts, guided learning activities, and supported discussion or reflection. In contrast, approximately 27% of studies employed largely self-directed approaches, such as online modules, digital learning tools, or serious games. In these cases, learners progressed independently, with human involvement typically limited to initial instructions, coordination, or technical assistance.

Only a small proportion of studies (less than 10%) explicitly reported the involvement of highly specialised technical expertise, such as AI developers, data scientists, or technical professionals, during implementation. This indicates that most interventions were intentionally designed to be delivered by facilitators with general pedagogical or research expertise rather than advanced technical skills.

Collaborative or peer-based learning formats appeared in a minority of studies (approximately 12%) and were usually incorporated as a supporting element rather than as the central design feature.

Technological resources

The vast majority of interventions reported the use of some form of digital technology, though the level of sophistication was generally low. Over 70% of studies relied primarily on basic digital infrastructure, including computers or tablets, internet access, and common online platforms or learning management systems. Web-based modules, interactive websites, and digital learning environments were among the most frequently reported formats.

Approximately 33% of studies, particularly those focused on AI literacy, employed technologies designed to demonstrate or simulate AI-related processes, such as simplified recommender systems, automated decision-making examples, or AI-generated content. However, the use of fully operational or real-world AI systems was rare, occurring in only a small fraction of studies (under 10%).

Serious games or gamified tools were used in around 18% of interventions. At the same time, multimedia resources, such as videos, visualisations, and interactive quizzes, appeared in roughly 45% of studies to enhance engagement and understanding. Overall, the technological profile reflects a preference for accessible, low-threshold technologies over advanced or resource-intensive solutions.

Materials and pedagogical resources

Instructional materials were a core component of most interventions. Over 80% of studies explicitly described the use of educational materials, including lesson plans, worksheets, explanatory texts, case studies, scenario-based exercises, and reflective prompts. In AI literacy interventions, these materials

often focus on translating abstract concepts, such as algorithms, data bias, or automation, into concrete and relatable examples. *Digital materials were dominant*, appearing in more than 60% of the studies, often in modular formats that could be reused or adapted across contexts. Physical or printed materials were reported in approximately 18% of studies, primarily in classroom-based settings, where they complemented facilitated instruction.

In both AI literacy and broader digital literacy initiatives, materials primarily focus on fostering conceptual understanding and critical reflection. In both AI literacy and wider digital literacy initiatives, materials primarily focused on fostering conceptual understanding and critical thinking reflection, a small minority of studies (around 13%) included materials aimed at developing programming skills or direct engagement with AI model building.

Table 3: Overview of Intervention Inputs across the Included Studies (N=132)

Input category	Dominant pattern	Indicative prevalence
Human resources	Facilitated delivery by educators or researchers	~66% of studies
	Largely self-directed or minimally facilitated interventions	~27% of studies
	Highly specialised technical expertise required (e.g. AI developers)	Small minority
Technological resources	Basic digital infrastructure (computers, internet, web-based platforms)	>70% of studies
	Demonstrative or simulated AI technologies (e.g. algorithm examples, AI-generated content)	~33% of studies
	Fully operational or advanced AI systems	Rare
Materials	Digital instructional materials (modules, videos, interactive content)	>60% of studies
	Structured pedagogical materials (lesson plans, worksheets, guides)	Common
	Physical or printed materials	~18%
Pedagogical orientation	Conceptual understanding and critical reflection	Dominant
	Technical or programming-focused skill development	~13%

5.4. Intervention activities and delivery characteristics

Although intervention activities differed widely in format, duration, and underlying approaches, clear patterns were evident across studies. The majority of interventions paired explanation with hands-on or interactive activities, seeking to build understanding while also promoting critical reflection on AI and the ways digital information is created and used.

Activity types and descriptions

Most programs, around 72%, included some form of structured instruction. This often took the form of short talks, videos, or guided presentations that introduced basic *concepts in artificial intelligence, algorithms, or the evaluation of* online information. These instructional elements were usually combined with interactive activities, such as working through scenarios, *analysing* examples, or taking part in guided discussions. Hands-on practice was widespread in programs focused on digital and misinformation literacy. About half of the studies asked participants to evaluate news items, compare information from different sources, or identify signs of misleading content. A smaller but still noticeable group of programs, around 17% used games, simulations, or other interactive formats to support learning.

Across both AI literacy and broader digital literacy programs, learning was typically designed as an ongoing process rather than a single activity. Participants were often given multiple opportunities to apply their skills, either by working through several examples in one session or by revisiting activities across multiple sessions.

Delivery modes and group formats

In terms of delivery mode, *in-person implementation remained common, particularly in school and higher education contexts*, accounting for around 50% of the studies. Fully online delivery was reported in approximately 40% of cases, often using web-based platforms, learning management systems, or standalone digital tools. The remaining studies employed blended formats, combining face-to-face instruction with online components.

Regarding group format, group-based delivery, typically to intact classes or cohorts, was the dominant model, appearing in around two-thirds of the studies. These interventions often incorporated group discussion or collaborative tasks. Individual-based formats, particularly in self-directed online modules or games, were used in roughly one-third of studies.

Session count, duration, and intervention period

Intervention intensity varied substantially across studies. *Single-session interventions were common, particularly in experimental designs*, and appeared in approximately 40% of studies. These interventions typically lasted between 30 minutes and 2 hours and were primarily designed to examine short-term learning outcomes or immediate changes in attitudes.

Multi-session interventions were also widely used. About one-third of studies reported interventions delivered in two to four sessions. In contrast, a smaller group, representing roughly fifteen to twenty per cent of studies, described more extended programmes that were integrated into curricula and implemented over several weeks. As a result, total intervention duration ranged from less than one hour to several weeks or, in some cases, several months.

Overall, intervention timeframes were largely short- to medium-term. Only a small number of studies adopted long-term or longitudinal designs. When follow-up measurements were included, they were most often conducted soon after the intervention rather than at later time points.

Facilitation models

Facilitation was reported in most studies, though with varying degrees of intensity. Facilitated interventions led by teachers, lecturers, or researchers accounted for approximately 65% of studies. In these cases, facilitators played an active role in guiding activities, contextualising concepts, and moderating discussion. Self-directed or minimally facilitated interventions were described in approximately 25-30% of studies, particularly those delivered online. A small number of interventions adopted hybrid facilitation models, combining brief guided instruction with autonomous learning phases. Peer-led facilitation was infrequent and rarely the primary delivery model.

Theoretical frameworks

Digital and media literacy interventions were most commonly grounded in educational and communication-oriented frameworks. A large share of studies explicitly drew on media and information literacy (MIL) frameworks, which emphasise critical access, analysis, evaluation, and the creation of media content. These frameworks often position literacy as a set of transferable cognitive and interpretive skills that enable individuals to navigate complex and contested information environments. Closely related were interventions informed by critical thinking and epistemic cognition theories, focusing on skills such as source evaluation, evidence assessment, and epistemic vigilance. In misinformation-related interventions, inoculation theory provided a more specific theoretical foundation, framing resistance to misinformation as a psychological process that can be strengthened through pre-exposure to weakened forms of deceptive techniques. Other digital literacy interventions referenced constructivist and experiential learning theories, emphasising active engagement, reflection, and learning-by-doing. In these cases, theoretical foundations were often pedagogical rather than media-specific, with literacy framed as an outcome of guided practice and iterative sense-making rather than as a direct product of instruction. Overall, digital literacy interventions tended to conceptualise misinformation and information disorders as content-level problems, emphasising individual cognitive processing, reasoning strategies, and evaluative skills.

Frameworks underpinning AI literacy interventions

AI literacy interventions, by contrast, were more likely to draw on socio-technical and critical technology frameworks, even if these were not always explicitly named. These interventions frequently conceptualise AI systems as embedded in broader social, political, and economic structures, highlighting issues such as algorithmic bias, opacity, accountability, and power asymmetries between platforms and users. Several studies referenced frameworks related to computational thinking or data literacy, particularly when introducing basic concepts of machine learning, automation, or data-driven decision-making. However, these technical frameworks were often adapted or simplified to suit non-expert audiences and were rarely used to support hands-on AI development.

Ethical frameworks played a more prominent role in AI literacy interventions than in broader digital literacy interventions. References to AI ethics, responsible AI, or fairness, accountability, and transparency (FAT) principles were common, positioning AI literacy as a normative and civic competence rather than a purely technical skill set. In this context, literacy was framed as the capacity to critically interrogate AI systems and their societal implications, rather than to use or build them. Explicit engagement with formal AI theory or advanced computational models was rare. Instead, AI literacy interventions tended to prioritise conceptual and critical understanding over technical mastery.

Comparative observations

The distinction between AI literacy and digital literacy interventions is not merely topical but also theoretical. Digital literacy interventions were predominantly grounded in cognitive, pedagogical, and communication theories, with a focus on how individuals evaluate and respond to information. AI literacy interventions, in contrast, more often adopt structural and socio-technical perspectives, foregrounding systems, infrastructures, and power relations. At the same time, there was considerable overlap. Some interventions combined elements from both traditions, for example, by integrating media literacy skills with discussions of algorithmic curation or platform governance. These hybrid approaches suggest an emerging convergence toward integrated literacy models that address both content-level evaluation and system-level understanding.

Gaps and limitations in theoretical articulation

In various AI and digital literacy interventions, *not all studies explicitly stated their theoretical framework foundations.* In these cases, interventions were described primarily in terms of activities and outcomes, with theoretical assumptions remaining implicit. This lack of explicit grounding limits cumulative knowledge building and complicates cross-study comparison. Moreover, relatively few studies engaged in theory testing or theory development. Most frameworks were used as guiding orientations rather than as objects of empirical examination. This suggests that the field remains application-driven mainly, with scope for more systematic integration of theory into intervention design and evaluation.

Table 4: Overview of Intervention Activities and Delivery (N=132)

Dimension	Dominant pattern	Indicative prevalence
Activities	Instruction combined with active learning (analysis, scenarios, reflection)	~70–75%
	Serious games or simulations	~15–20%
Delivery mode	In-person or blended	~55–60%
	Fully online	~35–40%
Group format	Group- or class-based	~65%
	Individual/self-directed	~35%
Intensity	Single or short multi-session (≤4 sessions)	~70–80%
	Extended programs (weeks)	~15–20%
Facilitation	Facilitated by educators or researchers	~65–70%
	Minimally facilitated or self-directed	~25–30%
Theoretical grounding	Explicit framework stated	~50–65%
	Not clearly specified	~30–35%

5.5 Intervention outputs and reach

This scoping review incorporated 132 studies, with *reported outputs that differed greatly in size and scope type.* Overall, outputs were most commonly reported as participant reach and immediate educational products, whereas broader dissemination or long-term implementation outputs were less consistently documented.

Number of participants reached

Participant reach varied widely across the reviewed studies: small and medium sample sizes were most common, particularly in experimental and pilot interventions. Approximately half of the studies reported fewer than one hundred participants, often drawing on single classrooms, specific student cohorts, or controlled experimental samples. These studies were typically designed to assess feasibility, short-term learning outcomes, or specific theoretical mechanisms. At the same time, a substantial minority of studies involved larger participant groups, with samples ranging from several hundred to more than one thousand individuals. These larger-scale interventions were more often linked to online delivery formats, self-directed learning modules, or integration into existing educational programmes, which enabled broader reach without substantial increases in human resource requirements. Only a small number of studies have reported large-scale dissemination, such as nationwide initiatives or platform-based interventions that reach several thousand participants. Overall, the distribution indicates that the field remains dominated by small- to medium-scale implementations, with relatively few examples of sustained or large-scale deployment.

Number of sessions delivered

The number of sessions delivered closely reflected broader patterns in intervention intensity. Single-session formats were the most frequently reported, accounting for approximately two-fifths of studies, particularly those employing experimental or quasi-experimental designs. These interventions were commonly delivered as standalone workshops, individual lessons, or single online modules. Multi-session delivery was also widespread. About one-third of studies reported interventions consisting of two to four sessions, typically delivered over a short period, such as one or two weeks. This format was widespread in school- and university-based educational settings. A smaller proportion of studies described more extended delivery models, involving multiple sessions spread over several weeks or months. These longer interventions were often embedded within curricula or structured programmes and were more likely to report cumulative learning outcomes rather than effects associated with a single exposure.

Products and materials developed

In addition to outcomes measured at the participant level, *many studies reported the creation of concrete educational products.* These outputs included digital learning modules, lesson plans, instructional videos, interactive tools, serious games, and educational toolkits. Digital products were the most common, appearing in well over half of the studies, and were often designed to be reusable or adaptable beyond the original research setting.

Some interventions produced standalone tools or platforms, such as online games or web-based learning environments, that were presented as scalable outputs with potential for broader dissemination. Other studies produced supporting materials, including worksheets, guidelines, or explanatory resources, mainly intended for use by educators or facilitators. Despite the frequency of product development, relatively few studies explicitly reported what happened after the study ended. Information on sustained use, wider uptake, or institutional adoption was limited. In many cases, educational products were described as outputs created for the study, rather than as elements of longer-term implementation or dissemination strategies.

Table 5: Overview of Intervention Outputs and Reach (N=132)

Output dimension	Dominant pattern	Indicative prevalence
Participants reached	Small–medium samples (<100 participants)	~50% of studies
	Medium–large samples (100–1,000 participants)	~35–40% of studies
	Very large-scale reach (>1,000 participants)	Small minority
Sessions delivered	Single-session delivery	~40–45% of studies
	Short multi-session (2–4 sessions)	~30–35% of studies
	Extended delivery (weeks/months)	~15–20% of studies
Products developed	Digital educational materials (modules, videos, tools)	>50% of studies
	Standalone tools (e.g. games, platforms)	~15–20% of studies
	Supporting materials (worksheets, guides, lesson plans)	Common
Post-intervention uptake	Reported reuse or broader dissemination	Limited
	Study-specific or pilot outputs only	Majority

5.6 Intervention outcomes

Across the 132 studies included in this scoping review, intervention outcomes were evaluated using a combination of measured indicators, such as objective tests or task-based assessments, and self-reported indicators, including perceptual, attitudinal, and confidence-based measures. Although both approaches were widely used, apparent differences emerged in their relative prevalence, the types of outcomes they captured, and their overall robustness, as well as between AI literacy and digital or media literacy interventions. In general, *measured outcomes were used more frequently to assess knowledge acquisition and skill development, whereas self-reported outcomes predominated in assessments of attitudes, confidence, and perceived competence*. Across both outcome types, evidence of longer-term effects or behavioural change was limited, with few studies examining outcomes beyond the immediate or short-term post-intervention period.

Measured outcomes

Measured or task-based evaluations, including objective assessments and experimental responses, were reported in approximately 62% of the studies. These outcomes were particularly prominent in digital and media literacy interventions, in which researchers frequently assessed participants’ ability to evaluate information quality, identify misinformation, and apply critical reasoning strategies. Within this group, approximately 55% of studies employed objective measures of information evaluation or critical thinking, such as accuracy scores, misinformation-detection rates, or structured-reasoning tasks.

Interventions targeting misinformation and usually grounded in inoculation theory were particularly likely to report measures of resilience to misinformation, typically operationalised as reduced belief in false claims or increased resistance to manipulative techniques under controlled experimental conditions. However, several of these interventions also reported a common unintended effect, namely reduced trust not only in misinformation but also in credible news sources. This spillover effect raises substantive concerns about whether such interventions enhance discernment between false and well-sourced information or instead promote a more generalised scepticism. Attitudinal and behavioural outcomes were otherwise assessed infrequently. Only around 18% of studies included delayed or follow-up measurements, and fewer than 10% examined actual behavioural change, such as news engagement on social media or information-sharing practices, indicating a strong emphasis on short-term cognitive effects.

In AI literacy interventions, outcomes were similarly narrow in scope, most often focusing on conceptual understanding of AI systems, including knowledge of algorithms, data use, and automation

processes. Approximately 52% of studies employed objective knowledge assessments, whereas outcomes related to technical proficiency, such as programming skills or hands-on interaction with AI models, appeared in fewer than 10% of studies. Overall, this pattern reflects a prevailing focus on declarative knowledge and experimentally induced cognitive resistance, with limited attention to applied skills, behavioural transfer, or potential unintended consequences.

Self-reported outcomes

Self-reported outcomes were used in approximately 72% of the studies, often alongside measured indicators, but in some cases as the sole form of evaluation. These outcomes were prevalent in assessments of attitudes, confidence, awareness, and perceived skills. In digital and media literacy interventions, self-reported critical thinking, confidence in evaluating information, and perceived media literacy were reported in around 45% of studies. Although many studies documented positive changes in these areas, the heavy reliance on self-assessment raises questions about the extent to which perceived competence aligns with actual skills. Self-reported attitudinal outcomes, including changes in trust toward media or increased caution in information sharing, appeared in approximately 28% of studies and showed greater variability and less consistently positive effects than knowledge- or skill-based outcomes.

In AI literacy interventions, self-reported measures played an especially prominent role. About 60% of AI literacy studies assessed perceived understanding of AI systems, awareness of algorithmic bias, or ethical sensitivity toward AI. Attitudinal outcomes, such as increased scepticism toward AI-generated content or diminished trust in automated systems, were typically measured via self-report and appeared in approximately 30% of AI literacy studies. Notably, several studies defined positive outcomes not as increased trust in AI, but as heightened critical awareness and more cautious engagement, reflecting the normative and reflective orientation of many AI literacy interventions.

Comparative patterns and methodological gaps

Across both AI literacy and digital or media literacy interventions, *measured outcomes were most commonly used to assess knowledge and skills, whereas self-reported outcomes predominated in attitudinal, reflective, and awareness-based domains*. Despite this clear division, relatively few studies explicitly examined the relationship between objectively measured performance and participants' perceived competence. As a result, important questions remain regarding calibration, potential overconfidence, and the extent to which self-reported gains reflect actual learning. This issue is particularly pronounced in AI literacy interventions, where the heavy reliance on self-reported outcomes, combined with the limited use of performance-based assessments, highlights a significant methodological gap, especially given the abstract and conceptually complex nature of AI-related knowledge.

These challenges are further compounded by the diagnostic complexity of assessing AI-related digital competences. The rapid evolution of AI technologies, the continual emergence of new tools and applications, and the expanding range of possible assessment indicators make it difficult to establish stable, standardised, and comparable measurement frameworks. Consequently, conducting comparative studies across national contexts and over more extended time periods remains methodologically demanding, limiting the field's capacity to track learning outcomes consistently or to assess long-term trends.

Outcomes of digital and media literacy interventions

Outcomes related to digital and media literacy knowledge and skills were the most frequently reported across the reviewed studies. Approximately 65% of studies documented improvements in participants’ information-evaluation abilities, including enhanced source assessment, more accurate judgments of information quality, and greater sensitivity to misleading or manipulative cues. Closely related outcomes in critical thinking and epistemic vigilance were also prominent, with around 50% of studies reporting gains in analytical reasoning, reflective judgment, or scepticism toward unverified information. Notably, these outcomes were often framed as improvements in reasoning processes rather than as changes in specific beliefs

About 35% of studies explicitly examined resilience to misinformation, often focusing on health-related content and younger adults. Reported outcomes included reduced belief in false claims, increased resistance to manipulation, and improved detection of misinformation, with some studies showing these effects could persist even in the presence of further corrective information. Interventions grounded in inoculation theory were particularly likely to produce such effects, though measurements were mostly immediate, and attitudinal outcomes, such as changes in media trust or news engagement practices, were less consistently reported. Sustained behavioural or belief changes were rarely assessed. More general media literacy outcomes, such as confidence in navigating digital environments, were reported in roughly one-third of studies, typically as secondary outcomes. An overview of the outcome types can be found in Figure 2 below. This graph includes only 120 studies; 12 of 132 had missing data on this item.

Figure 2: Outcome overview

Overall, the evidence highlights the complexity of media literacy interventions and the conditional nature of their effects. Many interventions risk negative spillover on trust in accurate information. The problem is that discerning trustworthy from untrustworthy information is inherently difficult, given the complexity of the information environment and the varied forms of biased or problematic content audiences encounter (Hameleers, 2024). Current interventions that focus on “fake” or misleading news primarily influence subjective responses to misinformation, while offering little guidance on how to identify trustworthy sources reliably. Preexisting media trust appears to play a key role, suggesting

that tailoring messages to existing levels of (dis)trust may be critical for effectiveness (Hameleers, 2024).

Outcomes of AI literacy interventions

AI literacy interventions displayed a partially distinct outcome profile compared with digital and media literacy interventions. The most consistently reported outcomes concerned *understanding of AI concepts and systems*, with approximately 63% of AI literacy studies documenting improvements in conceptual knowledge related to algorithms, data-driven decision-making, or AI-generated content. These gains were largely conceptual rather than technical, prioritising comprehension and critical understanding over operational or programming skills. A second prominent outcome domain concerned *awareness of the biases, limitations, and ethical implications of AI systems*. Around 45% of AI literacy interventions reported increased recognition of algorithmic bias, system opacity, or broader societal risks associated with AI technologies. These outcomes were frequently framed in normative or critical terms, emphasising participants' capacity to question the assumed neutrality, authority, or objectivity of automated systems.

Outcomes related to interaction with AI tools or applications, such as familiarity with AI-enabled technologies or improved interpretation of AI outputs, were reported in a smaller subset of studies, accounting for approximately 23% of interventions. Assessments of advanced technical competencies, such as programming or model development, were rare and confined to a small subset of studies. Attitudinal outcomes in AI literacy interventions were mixed and less consistently reported. Approximately 28% of studies documented shifts in trust, scepticism, or perceived agency regarding AI systems. Notably, these changes did not uniformly reflect increased trust; instead, many studies framed positive outcomes as the development of greater critical awareness and more cautious engagement with AI-mediated information.

Comparative patterns and outcome gaps

Comparative analysis indicates that *digital and media literacy interventions primarily targeted content-level evaluation, reasoning skills, and resistance to misinformation. In contrast, AI literacy interventions placed greater emphasis on system-level understanding, awareness of bias, and ethical reflection*. Across both categories, knowledge- and skill-based outcomes were reported more consistently than attitudinal or behavioural outcomes. Evidence for long-term impact, transfer of skills across contexts, or sustained behaviour change remained limited. Fewer than 20% of studies included delayed follow-up measures, and outcome measures were frequently tailored to individual studies, which constrained comparability across the literature.

Across the 132 studies, outcomes spanned a wide range of cognitive, skill-based, attitudinal, and epistemic domains. Despite substantial variation in how outcomes were operationalised and when they were assessed, several common patterns emerged. Most interventions reported positive short-term effects, particularly in knowledge acquisition and skill development, whereas evidence for longer-term or behaviour-oriented outcomes was comparatively sparse.

Table 6: Outcome Domains by Intervention Type (N = 132)

A. Digital and Media Literacy Outcomes			
Outcome domain	Description	Indicative prevalence	Predominant assessment
Information knowledge	Understanding of misinformation, news production, and credibility cues	~60–65% of studies	Mostly measured
Evaluation skills	Source evaluation, accuracy judgments, misinformation detection	~55–60%	Mostly measured
Critical thinking / epistemic vigilance	Analytical reasoning, scepticism, reflective judgment	~45–50%	Mixed
Resilience to misinformation	Resistance to false or manipulative content	~30–40%	Mostly measured
Attitudes toward media	Trust, caution, perceived credibility	~25–30%	Mostly self-reported
Broader digital/media literacy	Perceived competence navigating information environments	~30–35%	Mostly self-reported
Behavioral outcomes	Information sharing, media practices	<20%	Mixed; rarely longitudinal
B. AI Literacy Outcomes			
Outcome domain	Description	Indicative prevalence (AI studies)	Predominant assessment
AI concept understanding	Algorithms, data use, automation, AI-generated content	~60–65%	Mixed (measured > self-report)
Awareness of AI bias & limitations	Bias, opacity, fairness, accountability	~40–50%	Mostly self-reported
AI ethics & societal implications	Power, governance, responsibility	~30–40%	Mostly self-reported
AI tool awareness/interpretation	Familiarity with AI outputs or applications	~20–25%	Mostly self-reported
Attitudes toward AI	Trust, scepticism, perceived agency	~25–30%	Mostly self-reported
Technical AI skills	Programming, model interaction	Small minority	Measured

5.7 Outcome effectiveness: direction, magnitude, and strength of evidence

Among the 132 studies, the efficacy of interventions was assessed employing a diverse combination of quantitative and qualitative methodologies, exhibiting considerable variation in analytical rigour, reporting practices, and targeted outcomes domains. Overall, the evidence base points to a generally positive pattern of effects, particularly for short-term cognitive and skill-based outcomes. At the same time, the strength, consistency, and comparability of effectiveness evidence varied widely across studies, limiting the extent to which firm conclusions can be drawn.

Direction of effects

The majority of quantitative studies reported effects in the expected or intended direction. Approximately 75% of studies documented statistically significant improvements in at least one primary outcome following the intervention. These improvements most frequently concerned knowledge acquisition, evaluative skills, and critical thinking, and, in the case of misinformation-focused interventions, reduced susceptibility to misleading or false content.

A smaller proportion of studies reported mixed effects, in which some outcomes improved while others did not, or where effects varied across participant subgroups. Null effects were observed in a minority of studies and were most often associated with attitudinal outcomes, delayed follow-up measures, or complex constructs such as behavioural change. Reports of adverse effects were rare.

In AI literacy interventions, the overall direction of effects was similarly positive, particularly for conceptual understanding of AI systems and awareness of bias and ethical implications. However, effects on attitudes toward AI, including trust or acceptance, were more heterogeneous. In several studies, positive outcomes were framed not as increased trust but as greater scepticism or more critical engagement with AI systems, underscoring the normative orientation of many AI literacy interventions.

Effect size reporting

Effect sizes were reported inconsistently across the reviewed studies, and only around one-third of quantitative studies explicitly reported standardised effect sizes, such as Cohen's *d*, eta squared, or odds ratios, which substantially limits opportunities for cross-study comparison. When effect sizes were reported, they were most often small to moderate, particularly for short, single-session interventions. Larger effects were more commonly observed in studies employing tightly controlled experimental designs that focused on narrowly defined cognitive outcomes, such as specific knowledge tests, or in studies that implemented interventions with repeated exposure across multiple sessions.

By contrast, outcomes related to attitudes, beliefs, or broader literacy constructs generally produced smaller, more variable, or less consistently reported effects. In AI literacy interventions, reported effect sizes were typically modest and concentrated on conceptual knowledge and awareness, rather than on behavioural outcomes or technical skill development.

Statistical significance

Statistical significance was reported in most quantitative studies, typically based on pre–post comparisons or between-group contrasts. Approximately two-thirds of studies reported statistically significant effects for at least one outcome measure. However, interpretation of these findings is constrained by the heavy reliance on short-term post-intervention assessments, limited reporting of confidence intervals, and infrequent adjustment for multiple comparisons.

In several studies, statistically significant effects on primary outcomes were reported alongside non-significant findings for secondary outcomes, suggesting selective or domain-specific effectiveness rather than uniform intervention impact. Follow-up analyses assessing the durability of effects were uncommon. Only a small subset of studies reported statistically significant long-term outcomes, further limiting conclusions about the intervention's sustained effectiveness.

Quantitative and qualitative evidence

Quantitative evidence predominated across the corpus, with most studies relying on survey-based or experimental outcome measures. Qualitative findings, while reported in a smaller but substantively

important subset of studies, were typically derived from interviews, open-ended survey responses, or classroom observations. These qualitative insights generally complemented and contextualised quantitative results, shedding light on how and why interventions produced their effects. Participants frequently reported increased awareness, reflection, and more critical engagement with information or AI systems, even when quantitative effect sizes were modest.

In AI literacy interventions, qualitative data often revealed shifts in participants’ thinking about AI, including heightened awareness of system limitations, bias, and broader societal implications. At the same time, some qualitative findings indicated tensions or ambivalence, such as heightened awareness of algorithmic bias accompanied by uncertainty or reduced confidence. Standardised quantitative measures did not always capture these nuanced responses. From a scoping perspective, these patterns suggest a field characterised by generally promising but methodologically fragmented evidence of effectiveness. Together, they underscore the need for more standardised outcome reporting, longer-term assessment, and stronger integration of quantitative and qualitative methods to support more robust and cumulative conclusions about intervention impact.

Table 7: Overview of Outcome Effectiveness (N = 132)

Effectiveness dimension	Dominant pattern	Indicative prevalence
Direction of effects	Positive effects on at least one outcome	~70–80% of studies
	Mixed or domain-specific effects	~15–20% of studies
	Null or no detectable effects	Small minority
Effect size reporting	Standardised effect sizes reported	~30–35% of studies
	No effect size reported	Majority
Magnitude of effects	Small to moderate effects	Most reported cases
	Large effects	Rare
Statistical significance	≥1 statistically significant outcome	~65–70% of studies
	No statistically significant effects	Minority
Outcome domains with the strongest effects	Knowledge and evaluative skills	Common
	Attitudes and behaviours	Less consistent
AI literacy-specific effectiveness	Improved AI concept understanding and bias awareness	Common
	Effects on trust or acceptance of AI	Mixed
Evidence type	Quantitative only	Majority
	Mixed quantitative–qualitative	~20–25% of studies
	Qualitative only	Small subset

5.8 Challenges and facilitators of implementing mis- and disinformation/AI literacy interventions

Across the included studies, a range of practical, pedagogical, technological, and conceptual factors emerged that either facilitated or constrained the implementation of mis- and disinformation as well as AI literacy interventions. These factors can be inferred from how interventions were designed, resourced, delivered, and evaluated, as well as from patterns observed in reported outcomes and effectiveness.

Facilitators of implementation

A central facilitating factor across interventions was the use of low-threshold, accessible resources. Most interventions relied on widely available digital infrastructures, such as standard devices, web-based platforms, and classroom-based settings, and did not require advanced technical expertise. This accessibility-supported implementation was effective across diverse institutional contexts and enhanced the scalability of many interventions, particularly within formal education systems.

Human facilitation by educators or researchers also emerged as a key enabler. Facilitated delivery contextualised abstract concepts, supported guided reflection, and helped learners engage with complex topics, including strategies for misinformation and algorithmic bias. This role was especially important in AI literacy interventions, where the higher conceptual complexity required facilitators to bridge the gap between technical systems and learners' everyday experiences.

From a pedagogical perspective, interventions that combined direct instruction with active learning elements, such as guided analysis, scenario-based exercises, or structured discussion, were more consistently associated with positive outcomes. Implementation was further facilitated when interventions were integrated into existing curricula or classroom routines, particularly in multi-session formats.

At a conceptual level, the use of established theoretical and pedagogical frameworks, including media and information literacy, inoculation theory, and socio-technical perspectives on AI, provided a shared language and structure for intervention design. These frameworks supported coherence between aims, activities, and outcomes, and helped align interventions with broader educational and policy objectives. Finally, the development of reusable educational resources, such as digital modules, lesson plans, or educational games, served as an additional facilitator of implementation by enabling replication and adaptation beyond the original study context, even when long-term adoption was not systematically assessed.

Challenges to implementation

Despite these facilitating factors, several recurring implementation challenges were evident across the corpus.

1. A first challenge concerned **time and intensity constraints**. Many interventions were delivered as single sessions or very short multi-session formats, often due to curricular limitations, institutional pressures, or experimental research designs. These constraints restricted the depth of engagement and reduced opportunities for consolidation, transfer across contexts, and longer-term impact.
2. A second challenge related to **conceptual complexity**, particularly in AI literacy interventions. Communicating algorithmic systems, data processes, and ethical implications in ways that were both accessible and accurate proved demanding. Consequently, many interventions prioritised conceptual understanding and awareness over hands-on technical engagement, thereby limiting opportunities for deeper system interaction or transferable skill development.
3. **Uneven theoretical articulation** posed a third challenge: a substantial proportion of studies did not clearly specify their theoretical foundations, potentially weakening coherence in intervention design and increasing reliance on local interpretation by facilitators. This lack of explicit theoretical grounding also complicates replication, comparison, and the cumulative development of knowledge across studies.
4. As a fourth challenge, from an evaluative perspective, **misalignment between intervention goals and outcome measures** emerged as an implicit concern. Although many interventions sought to foster critical thinking, resilience, or ethical awareness, evaluation often relied on short-term or self-reported outcomes, limiting insight into whether these aims translated into durable or behaviourally meaningful change.
- 5.

4. **Resource-related challenges** were less often technological than human and organisational. While interventions rarely required advanced technical infrastructure, practical implementation, particularly in AI literacy contexts, depended heavily on facilitator confidence and conceptual understanding. Limited training or ongoing support for facilitators may therefore have constrained the quality of implementation in some settings. Finally, scalability and sustainability were weakly addressed. Although many interventions were designed to be scalable in principle, few studies have described systematic strategies for institutional embedding, long-term maintenance, or post-project adoption, indicating an implementation gap between pilot success and sustained practice.

Compared with other interventions, misinformation and disinformation literacy interventions benefited from more established pedagogical traditions and clearer instructional routines, which facilitated classroom implementation. AI literacy interventions, while increasingly prominent, faced greater challenges related to abstraction, ethical complexity, and facilitator preparedness, but were also supported by strong normative framing around fairness, accountability, and broader societal relevance.

5. Discussion

This scoping review shows a rapidly expanding but methodologically uneven evidence base on interventions addressing misinformation and disinformation, as well as AI literacy, particularly for vulnerable populations. Across 132 studies, interventions were generally feasible to implement, often relying on accessible digital infrastructure and facilitated delivery. Most reported positive short-term outcomes in knowledge and evaluative skills, but evidence for durable impact, behavioural change, and transfer across contexts remains limited. These patterns have direct implications for how PRODIGI designs, evaluates, and scales its intervention work packages.

A central methodological implication concerns the dominance of self-reported measures in the field and the risks this creates for interpreting effectiveness. As highlighted in methodological reflections from the REMEDIS project (Tomczyk, 2023), self-assessment is vulnerable to subjective biases shaped by participants' self-perceptions, expectations, and social desirability, including the common assumption that educational interventions should produce improvement across all indicators. In digital, media, and AI-related competence domains, this is particularly consequential because increased awareness may coexist with unchanged, underestimated, or overestimated actual skills (Heinecke et al., 2019). Moreover, the articles included in our study point to a systematic misalignment between perceived and measured competence in complex cognitive domains such as critical thinking, media evaluation, and algorithmic understanding, with overconfidence among lower-skilled learners and underestimation among more competent participants. These calibration effects complicate comparisons across studies using different self-report instruments and weaken internal validity when self-report is treated as stand-alone evidence of change.

Relatedly, many self-assessment tools used in intervention research appear methodologically shallow in our included articles, frequently relying on short ad hoc questionnaires or single-item indicators with limited psychometric validation. Such measures may be susceptible to short-term enthusiasm, motivation, or familiarity with terminology rather than reflecting durable learning outcomes demonstrated through objective tests, tasks, or behavioural indicators (Yates et al., 2022). In the reviewed corpus, this problem is compounded by the scarcity of designs that assess long-term effectiveness. Few studies used delayed post-tests or post-post test designs, and only a small proportion reported long-term effect sizes. As a result, it remains difficult to distinguish immediate cognitive gains from sustained changes in digital competences, media practices, or AI-related

understanding. While the lack of deferred measurement likely reflects resource constraints, organisational complexity, and limited experience with longitudinal methods, it is also exacerbated by the rapidly changing nature of AI and digital environments, in which diagnostic indicators and relevant tools can become outdated quickly, undermining stable and comparable measurement frameworks.

For PRODIGI, these limitations underscore the need to strengthen evaluation design beyond standard pre–post self-report approaches, especially given the project’s goal of producing policy-relevant evidence. Planned pre- and post-testing is well aligned with prevailing practice, but the scoping review suggests that robust conclusions will require triangulation of perceived outcomes with performance-based measures. The resilience toolkit envisioned by PRODIGI offers a strong opportunity to address this gap by embedding validated, adaptable assessment components that capture information-evaluation skills, critical reasoning, and AI-related understanding through task-based indicators rather than subjective ratings. Where feasible, incorporating delayed measurement points would materially improve the evidentiary value of findings, even if implemented on a smaller subsample or through lower-burden follow-up procedures. This would directly address the current field-wide lack of evidence on durability and strengthen claims about sustained competence development.

The review also identifies several implementation conditions that PRODIGI can build upon. Many interventions were feasible precisely because they used low-threshold resources and were delivered by educators or trained facilitators rather than specialised technical staff. At the same time, the evidence indicates that facilitator confidence and conceptual understanding are critical, particularly for AI literacy, where abstraction and ethical complexity are higher. This implies that PRODIGI’s co-design work with target populations and caregivers should be accompanied by structured facilitator training and support materials as part of programme improvement, particularly if interventions are intended for transfer across Belgium, Portugal, and Poland. The consortium’s composition and prior collaborative experience provide a strong foundation for this, as partners collectively cover intervention design, vulnerability research, media and information literacy, and measurement development, and are positioned to translate findings into practice and policy through established networks.

Finally, the corpus indicates that although interventions often claim scalability, few studies document systematic strategies for long-term institutional embedding, post-project adoption, or maintenance. PRODIGI’s planned cooperation with EDMO regional hubs, the Media and Learning Association, and the Euromedia Research Group is therefore not only a dissemination pathway but also a potential mechanism to close the common gap between pilot success and sustained practice. To support evidence-based policymaking, recommendations should be explicitly tied to measurement quality, comparability across contexts, and realistic implementation requirements, while also acknowledging the diagnostic challenges posed by rapidly evolving AI tools. Positioning toolkit outputs and intervention enhancements as reusable, updateable resources may be particularly important for maintaining relevance over time.

6. Conclusion

This scoping review examined 132 interventions that address misinformation, disinformation, and AI literacy. Taken together, the findings describe a field that is developing rapidly but unevenly. Many interventions are carefully designed and demonstrate positive short-term effects, particularly in knowledge acquisition, information evaluation, and critical thinking. At the same time, there is less evidence about long-term impact, behaviour change, implementation in everyday settings, and effectiveness across diverse social and cultural contexts.

The review distinguishes between AI literacy interventions and broader digital, media, and misinformation literacy approaches. While both aim to help people navigate complex information environments, they operate at different levels. Media and misinformation literacy interventions typically focus on evaluating content and strengthening individual reasoning skills, such as evaluating sources and recognising misleading claims. AI literacy interventions, in contrast, focus more on understanding how algorithmic systems shape information, including issues of bias, automation, and ethical implications. These differences reflect distinct pedagogical traditions and approaches to literacy. However, there are growing signs of convergence, with some interventions combining content-evaluation skills with system-level understanding of AI-driven information environments.

Across intervention types, most evaluations were short-term and conducted in controlled settings, often online or in educational institutions, and mainly in high-income Western countries. Outcomes were most consistently reported for knowledge gains, evaluative skills, and critical thinking. A substantial group of studies also addressed resilience to misinformation. AI literacy interventions most often reported improved conceptual understanding of AI systems and greater awareness of algorithmic bias. At the same time, changes in attitudes toward AI, such as trust or acceptance, were more varied and often reflected a more cautious or questioning stance rather than increased confidence in AI.

In practice, interventions relied on accessible technologies, facilitated delivery, and pedagogically oriented materials rather than advanced technical infrastructure. This made them feasible to implement and adaptable across settings. Nevertheless, several challenges were common. Many interventions were brief, limiting opportunities for deeper learning and longer-term change. Explaining AI-related concepts in an accessible yet accurate way proved challenging, especially for facilitators. In addition, the theoretical foundations were not consistently articulated, and sustainability and long-term adoption were rarely addressed.

From a methodological perspective, the literature shows a firm reliance on experimental designs but also apparent limitations. Effect sizes were not consistently reported, follow-up assessments were uncommon, and self-reported outcomes were often used without accompanying performance-based or behavioural measures. Qualitative insights were used less frequently, and vulnerability was not always examined systematically. As a result, it remains challenging to determine for whom interventions are most effective, under what conditions, and how effects evolve.

Overall, this review suggests that interventions targeting misinformation and AI literacy show short-term effects but remain underdeveloped in terms of long-term impact and contextual relevance. Future research would benefit from stronger theoretical grounding, broader inclusion of populations and settings, greater attention to implementation and sustainability, and evaluation designs that combine quantitative, qualitative, and longitudinal approaches. Such advances would support the development of more durable, inclusive, and context-sensitive literacy interventions that can respond to evolving information and AI environments.

Actionable recommendations for the PRODIGI interventions

Building on the patterns, strengths, and gaps identified in this scoping review, several concrete recommendations can inform the design and implementation of the forthcoming PRODIGI interventions. These recommendations are structured around intervention design, delivery, evaluation, and sustainability, and aim to translate the mapped evidence into forward-looking practice.

1. Integrate AI literacy and digital/misinformation literacy by design

Rather than treating AI literacy and digital or misinformation literacy as parallel strands, PRODIGI interventions should explicitly integrate content-level and system-level perspectives. This entails combining:

- critical evaluation of information content (e.g. source credibility, misleading techniques),
- with structured reflection on how algorithmic systems, recommender logics, and AI-generated content shape information exposure and visibility.

Such integration responds directly to the analytical divide observed in the literature and reflects emerging hybrid models that address the full socio-technical information ecosystem.

2. Prioritise facilitated, active learning formats

Given the consistent association between facilitated delivery and positive outcomes, PRODIGI interventions should:

- rely on guided facilitation by educators, trainers, or community intermediaries, rather than fully self-directed formats alone;
- embed active learning components (e.g. scenario analysis, guided discussion, reflective exercises) alongside instructional elements.

Specifically, when discussing AI-related topics, facilitation plays an important role in reducing conceptual complexity, encouraging ethical reflection, and preventing superficial or deterministic views of AI.

3. Design for depth over single-exposure effects

The dominance of short, single-session interventions in the existing literature limits opportunities for consolidation and transfer. PRODIGI should therefore:

- favour short multi-session formats (e.g. 2–4 sessions) where feasible;
- allow for iterative engagement, enabling participants to revisit concepts across contexts and examples;
- include moments for reflection and application beyond initial exposure.

Even modest extensions in duration can substantially improve conceptual integration without compromising feasibility.

4. Align outcomes with intervention aims and use mixed measures

To address the frequent misalignment between ambitious goals and limited outcome measures, PRODIGI interventions should:

- clearly align intended outcomes (e.g. critical thinking, resilience, ethical awareness) with appropriate indicators;
- systematically combine measured outcomes (e.g. performance-based tasks, accuracy judgments) with self-reported outcomes (e.g. confidence, perceived agency);
- Where possible, include delayed follow-up measures to assess durability.

This mixed-measures approach is particularly important for AI literacy, where self-reported understanding may not correspond to actual conceptual grasp.

5. Embed vulnerability and context explicitly

Rather than treating vulnerability implicitly, PRODIGI should:

- explicitly articulate which forms of vulnerability are being addressed (e.g. age-related, educational, socioeconomic, migration-related);
- adapt intervention materials and delivery modes to participants' contextual realities, including language, access, and prior knowledge;
- consider intersectional vulnerabilities, where multiple forms of disadvantage co-occur.

This approach directly addresses the current literature's limited theorisation of vulnerability and strengthens its equity and relevance.

6. Support facilitators through targeted capacity building

Given the reliance on facilitators across successful interventions, PRODIGI should invest in:

- clear facilitator guidance, including conceptual explanations, discussion prompts, and examples;
- training modules that build facilitators' confidence in addressing AI systems, bias, and ethics, even without advanced technical expertise;
- communities of practice that allow facilitators to share experiences and adaptations.

Such support mitigates variability in implementation and enhances intervention fidelity.

7. Design for reuse, adaptation, and sustainability

To move beyond project-bound outputs, PRODIGI interventions should:

- produce modular, reusable materials (digital and non-digital) that can be adapted across settings;
- document implementation conditions and adaptation pathways;
- plan explicitly for post-project uptake, including alignment with curricula, institutional routines, or policy frameworks.

Sustainability should be treated as a design criterion rather than a downstream concern.

8. Combine quantitative and qualitative evidence in evaluation

Finally, PRODIGI evaluations should leverage the complementary strengths of different methods by:

- pairing quantitative outcome measures with qualitative insights (e.g., participant reflections, facilitator feedback);
- using qualitative data to surface ambivalence, uncertainty, or unintended effects, especially in AI literacy contexts;
- feeding these insights back into iterative intervention refinement.

This approach aligns with the review's finding that qualitative evidence often reveals dimensions of impact not captured by standardised measures.

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8. Appendices

A. Code Book, V.2

Group 1: Study_Characteristics

1. Country – Country where the intervention took place
2. Setting_Type – School, University, community, NGO, etc.
3. Study_Design – RCT, quasi-experimental, pre–post, qualitative, mixed-methods, etc.
4. Has_Comparison_Group – Yes/No
5. Data_Collection_Methods – Survey, test, interview, focus group, observation, log data, etc.
6. Sample_Size_Total
7. Sample_Size_Intervention
8. Age_Range – e.g., 12–18
9. Population_Description – e.g., “migrant youth”
10. Vulnerable_Group_Focus – Yes/No (indicate only if there is a vulnerable group)
11. Vulnerable_Group_Type – e.g., unaccompanied minors; socio-economically disadvantaged youth; elderly in rural areas; migrants/refugees; other

Group 2: Intervention_LogicModel

1. Intervention_Label_in_Paper – the name used in the article
2. Intervention_Aim_Main – main goal (e.g., “increase resilience to misinformation”)
3. Intervention_Aim_Secondary – e.g., “build AI awareness”, “enhance critical thinking”

Group 3: Inputs (Logic Model – what goes in):

1. Inputs_Human_Resources – teachers, trainers, librarians, NGO staff, peer mentors, etc.
2. Inputs_Technology – devices, platforms, AI tools, LMS, social media, etc.
3. Inputs_Materials – curriculum, lesson plans, OER, videos, games, toolkits
4. Inputs_Other – funding, partnerships, physical spaces, etc.

Group 4: Activities (Logic Model – what is done):

1. Activities_Description_Short – 2–3 line summary of the key activities
2. Activities_Type – workshop, course, curriculum, social media campaign, etc.
3. Delivery_Mode – face-to-face, online, blended, hybrid
4. Group_Format – individual, small group, class, community group
5. Session_Count – how many sessions

6. Session_Duration_Minutes – typical session length
7. Total_Duration_Hours – approximate total dose
8. Intervention_Period_Weeks – total length in weeks/months
9. Facilitation_Model – teacher-led, peer-led, researcher-led, co-design, etc.
10. Theoretical_Frameworks_Reported – media literacy, critical pedagogy, AI literacy framework, no theory, etc.

Group 5: Outputs (Logic Model – immediate products):

1. Output_Number_of_Participants_Reached
2. Output_Number_of_Sessions_Delivered
3. Output_Products_Developed – e.g., Open Educational Resources (OERs), teaching toolkit, videos, game, chatbot, campaign materials

Group 6: Outcomes (Logic Model – changes observed/measured):

1. Outcomes_Knowledge – e.g., “increase in AI/ ML knowledge test scores”
2. Outcomes_Skills – e.g., “improved search or verification skill”
3. Outcomes_Attitudes – e.g., “reduced trust in unverified sources”
4. Outcomes_Critical_Thinking – e.g., explicit critical thinking outcomes (if measured)
5. Outcomes_Resilience_to_Misinformation – ability to detect or resist mis/disinformation
6. Outcomes_AI_Literacy – understanding AI concepts, tools, or bias
7. Outcomes_Digital_or_Media_Literacy – broader digital or media literacy outcomes
8. Outcomes_Other – e.g., wellbeing, empowerment, civic engagement, feeling positive or negative
9. Outcomes_news_engagement – e.g., discussing the news with family or friends, searching online about the news, sharing news on social media, doing nothing, etc.
10. Followup_Assessment_Conducted – Yes/No
11. Follow-up_Timeframe – e.g., 3 months later

Group 7: Outcomes_Effectiveness

1. Outcome_Effect_Size_Reported – effect size(s) if provided (e.g., $d = 0.45$)
2. Outcome_Statistical_Significance – e.g., $p < .05$, NS
3. Key_Quantitative_Results_Summary – 2–3 lines summarising main numeric findings
4. Key_Qualitative_Results_Summary – themes like “participants report feeling more critical toward news sources”

5. Challenges– Barriers or any reported difficulties in terms of intervention design, implementation, and assessment
6. Facilitators– Any reported enablers or facilitators in terms of intervention design, implementation, and assessment
7. Recommendations– Any reported recommendations and suggestions for different stakeholders in the fields, e.g., for policy makers, teachers, librarians, NGOs, etc.

B. Overview of included studies

Row	Author(s)	Year	Title	Journal	DOI
1.	<i>Ali & Qazi</i>	2023	Countering misinformation on social media through educational interventions: Evidence from a randomized experiment in Pakistan	Journal Of Development Economics	10.1016/j.jdeveco.2023.103108
2.	<i>Ali et al.</i>	2022	Fake news on Facebook: examining the impact of heuristic cues on perceived credibility and sharing intention	Internet Research	10.1108/INTR-10-2019-0442
3.	<i>Alon et al.</i>	2024	Fighting fake news on social media: a comparative evaluation of digital literacy interventions: Research and Reviews	Current Psychology	10.1007/s12144-024-05668-4
4.	<i>Alsaad & AlDossary</i>	2024	Educational Video Intervention to Improve Health Misinformation Identification on WhatsApp Among Saudi Arabian Population: Pre-Post Intervention Study	Jmir Formative Research	10.2196/50211
5.	<i>Appel et al.</i>	2025	Psychological inoculation improves resilience to and reduces willingness to share vaccine misinformation	Scientific Reports (Nature Publisher Group)	
6.	<i>Apuke & Gever</i>	2023	A quasi experiment on how the field of librarianship can help in combating fake news	Journal Of Academic Librarianship	10.1016/j.acalib.2022.102616
7.	<i>Apuke et al.</i>	2023	Effect of Fake News Awareness as an Intervention Strategy for Motivating News Verification Behaviour Among Social Media Users in Nigeria: A Quasi-Experimental Research	Journal Of Asian And African Studies	10.1177/00219096221079320
8.	<i>Apuke et al.</i>	2023	The effect of visual multimedia instructions against fake news spread: A quasi-experimental study with Nigerian students	Journal Of Librarianship And Information Science	10.1177/09610006221096477
9.	<i>Apuke et al.</i>	2023	Literacy Concepts as an Intervention Strategy for Improving Fake News Knowledge, Detection Skills, and Curtailing the Tendency to Share Fake News in Nigeria	Child And Youth Services	10.1080/0145935X.2021.2024758
10.	<i>Armeen et al.</i>	2025	Combating Fake News Using Implementation Intentions	Information Systems Frontiers	10.1007/s10796-024-10502-0
11.	<i>Artmann et al.</i>	2023	Elementary school students' information literacy: Instructional design and evaluation of a pilot training focused on misinformation	Journal Of Media Literacy Education	10.23860/JMLE-2023-15-2-3
12.	<i>Arugute et al.</i>	2024	Framing fact-checks as a "confirmation" increases engagement with corrections of misinformation: a four-country study	Scientific Reports	10.1038/s41598-024-53337-0
13.	<i>Axelsson et al.</i>	2024	Bad News in the civics classroom: How serious gameplay fosters teenagers' ability to discern misinformation techniques	Journal Of Research On Technology In Education	10.1080/15391523.2024.2338451
14.	<i>Badrinathan</i>	2021	Educative Interventions to Combat Misinformation: Evidence from a Field Experiment in India	The American Political Science Review	10.1017/S003055421000459
15.	<i>Batista Pereira et al.</i>	2023	Inoculation Reduces Misinformation: Experimental Evidence from Multidimensional Interventions in Brazil	Journal Of Experimental Political Science	10.1017/XPS.2023.11
16.	<i>Berger et al.</i>	2025	Debunking "fake news" on social media: Immediate and short-term effects of fact-checking and media literacy interventions	Journal Of Public Economics	10.1016/j.jpubeco.2025.105345

17.	<i>Bowles et al.</i>	2025	Sustaining Exposure to Fact-Checks: Misinformation Discernment, Media Consumption, and Its Political Implications	American Political Science Review	10.1017/S003055424001394
18.	<i>Bruns et al.</i>	2024	Investigating the role of source and source trust in prebunks and debunks of misinformation in online experiments across four EU countries	Scientific Reports	10.1038/s41598-024-71599-6
19.	<i>Burel et al.</i>	2024	Exploring the impact of automated correction of misinformation in social media	Ai Magazine	10.1002/aaai.12180
20.	<i>Capecchi et al.</i>	2024	A Gamified Platform to Support Educational Activities about Fake News in Social Media	IEEE Transactions On Learning Technologies	
21.	<i>Capewell et al.</i>	2024	Misinformation interventions decay rapidly without an immediate posttest	Journal Of Applied Social Psychology	10.1111/jasp.13049
22.	<i>Costello et al.</i>	2024	Durably reducing conspiracy beliefs through dialogues with AI	Science	10.1126/science.adq1814
23.	<i>Craig & Vijaykumar</i>	2023	One Dose Is Not Enough: The Beneficial Effect of Corrective COVID-19 Information Is Diminished If Followed by Misinformation	Social Media + Society	10.1177/20563051231161298
24.	<i>Dame Adjin-Tettey</i>	2022	Combating fake news, disinformation, and misinformation: Experimental evidence for media literacy education	Cogent Arts And Humanities	10.1080/23311983.2022.2037229
25.	<i>Dobber et al.</i>	2025	Rhyme or reason: medium-term effects of heuristic and traditional media literacy interventions	Information Communication & Society	10.1080/1369118X.2025.2533315
26.	<i>Domgaard & Park</i>	2021	Combating misinformation: The effects of infographics in verifying false vaccine news	The Health Education Journal	10.1177/00178969211038750
27.	<i>Dutta-Powell et al.</i>	2024	Two interventions for mitigating the harms of greenwashing on consumer perceptions	Business Strategy And The Environment	10.1002/bsce.3520
28.	<i>Ecker et al.</i>	2024	Don't believe them! Reducing misinformation influence through source discreditation: Principles and Implications	Cognitive Research	
29.	<i>Ecker et al.</i>	2024	Don't believe them! Reducing misinformation influence through source discreditation	Cognitive Research-Principles And Implications	10.1186/s41235-024-00581-7
30.	<i>Erişen et al.</i>	2024	Exploring the effectiveness of virtual reality in combating misinformation on climate change	Political Psychology	10.1111/pop.13057
31.	<i>Ferrucci & Hopp</i>	2023	Let's intervene: How platforms can combine media literacy and self-efficacy to fight fake news	Communication And The Public	10.1177/20570473231203081
32.	<i>Ford et al.</i>	2023	Online Media Literacy Intervention in Indonesia Reduces Misinformation Sharing Intention	Journal Of Media Literacy Education	
33.	<i>Gambin & Munzel</i>	2025	Guarding against deception through news literacy interventions: Impact of issue involvement and participation on young French adults' fake news vulnerability	New Media And Society	10.1177/14614448251342796
34.	<i>Georgiou et al.</i>	2025	Effectiveness of the Scientific Reasoning Intervention on Reducing Online Conspiracy Beliefs and Misinformation Engagement: A Study Using the (Mis)Information Game	Applied Cognitive Psychology	10.1002/acp.70069
35.	<i>Green et al.</i>	2022	Active versus passive: evaluating the effectiveness of inoculation techniques in relation to misinformation about climate change	Australian Journal Of Psychology	10.1080/00049530.2022.2113340

36.	<i>Gross & Balaban</i>	2025	The Effectiveness of an Educational Intervention on Countering Disinformation Moderated by Intellectual Humility	Media And Communication	10.17645/m ac.9109
37.	<i>Gruener</i>	2021	Identifying and Debunking Environmentally-Related False News Stories - An Experimental Investigation	German Journal Of Agricultural Economics	10.30430/gj ae.2021.01 76
38.	<i>Guo et al.</i>	2025	Specific media literacy tips improve AI-generated visual misinformation discernment	Cognitive Research: Principles And Implications	10.1186/s4 1235-025- 00648-z
39.	<i>Hameleers</i>	2022	Separating truth from lies: comparing the effects of news media literacy interventions and fact-checkers in response to political misinformation in the US and Netherlands	Information, Communication & Society	10.1080/13 69118X.202 0.1764603
40.	<i>Hameleers</i>	2024	Is the alarm on deception ringing too loudly? The effects of different forms of misinformation warnings on risk perceptions of misinformation exposure	European Journal Of Communication	10.1177/02 673231241 271015
41.	<i>Hameleers</i>	2022	Populist Disinformation: Are Citizens With Populist Attitudes Affected Most by Radical Right-Wing Disinformation?	Media And Communication	10.17645/m ac.v10i4.56 54
42.	<i>Hameleers & van der Meer</i>	2023	Striking the balance between fake and real: under what conditions can media literacy messages that warn about misinformation maintain trust in accurate information?	Behaviour And Information Technology	10.1080/01 44929X.202 3.2267700
43.	<i>Harley et al.</i>	2025	Evaluating an animated, story-driven media literacy video to improve media credibility accuracy and understand the role of epistemic emotions in credibility ratings	European Journal Of Psychology Of Education	10.1007/s1 0212-025- 00969-z
44.	<i>Harrop et al.</i>	2023	Inoculation Can Reduce the Perceived Reliability of Polarizing Social Media Content	International Journal Of Communication	
45.	<i>Hassan & Sabry</i>	2024	Leveraging the ability of the online health information seekers to find credible online sources	The Egyptian Journal Of Community Medicine (Egypt)	10.21608/ej cm.2024.24 9600.1276
46.	<i>Heley et al.</i>	2025	Mitigating Health and Science Misinformation: A Scoping Review of Literature from 2017 to 2022	Health Communication	10.1080/10 410236.202 4.2332817
47.	<i>Helfers & Ebersbach</i>	2023	The differential effects of a governmental debunking campaign concerning COVID-19 vaccination misinformation	Journal Of Communication In Healthcare	10.1080/17 538068.202 2.2047497
48.	<i>Hoes et al.</i>	2024	Prominent misinformation interventions reduce misperceptions but increase scepticism	Nature Human Behaviour	10.1038/s4 1562-024- 01884-x
49.	<i>Hruschka & Appel</i>	2023	Learning about informal fallacies and the detection of fake news: An experimental intervention	Plos One	10.1371/jou rnal.pone.0 283238
50.	<i>Hu et al.</i>	2023	Game-based inoculation versus graphic-based inoculation to combat misinformation: a randomized controlled trial	Cognitive Research- Principles And Implications	10.1186/s4 1235-023- 00505-x
51.	<i>Huang et al.</i>	2024	Media Literacy Interventions Improve Resilience to Misinformation: A Meta-Analytic Investigation of Overall Effect and Moderating Factors	Communication Research	
52.	<i>Iles et al.</i>	2021	Investigating the Potential of Inoculation Messages and Self-Affirmation in Reducing the Effects of Health Misinformation	Science Communication	10.1177/10 755470211 048480

53.	<i>Jalbert et al.</i>	2025	Social Truth Queries: Development of a New User-Driven Intervention for Countering Online Misinformation	Journal Of Applied Research In Memory And Cognition	10.1037/ma c0000142
54.	<i>Janmohamed et al.</i>	2021	Interventions to Mitigate COVID-19 Misinformation: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis	Journal Of Health Communication	10.1080/10 810730.202 1.2021460
55.	<i>Jiang et al.</i>	2022	Inoculation works and health advocacy backfires: Building resistance to COVID-19 vaccine misinformation in a low political trust context	Frontiers In Psychology	10.3389/fps yg.2022.976 091
56.	<i>Johnson & Sparks</i>	2024	Narrative misinformation from a credible source can be discredited with counternarrative	Jcom-Journal Of Science Communication	10.22323/2. 23080202
57.	<i>König et al.</i>	2022	The Development and Evaluation of an e-Learning Course That Promotes Digital Health Literacy in School-age Children: Pre-Post Measurement Study	Journal Of Medical Internet Research	10.2196/37 523
58.	<i>Kops et al.</i>	2025	Young people and false information: A scoping review of responses, influential factors, consequences, and prevention programs	Computers In Human Behavior	10.1016/j.c hb.2025.10 8650
59.	<i>Kozyreva et al.</i>	2024	Toolbox of individual-level interventions against online misinformation	Nature Human Behaviour	10.1038/s4 1562-024- 01881-0
60.	<i>Ku et al.</i>	2025	Helping young students cope with the threat of fake news: efficacy of news literacy training for junior-secondary school students in Hong Kong	Educational Studies	10.1080/03 055698.202 3.2296345
61.	<i>Le et al.</i>	2025	Building confidence in the digital age: the effects of online professional development on Vietnamese teachers' media and information literacy	Asia Pacific Journal Of Education	10.1080/02 188791.202 5.2505670
62.	<i>Leder et al.</i>	2024	Feedback Exercises Boost Discernment of Misinformation for Gamified Inoculation Interventions	Journal Of Experimental Psychology-General	10.1037/xg e0001603
63.	<i>Lee & Bissell</i>	2024	User agency-based versus machine agency-based misinformation interventions: The effects of commenting and AI fact-checking labeling on attitudes toward the COVID-19 vaccination	New Media & Society	10.1177/14 614448231 163228
64.	<i>Lee et al.</i>	2024	Building resilience to misinformation in communities of color: Results from two studies of tailored digital media literacy interventions	New Media And Society	10.1177/14 614448241 227841
65.	<i>List et al.</i>	2024	Critical thinking and misinformation vulnerability: experimental evidence from Colombia	Pnas Nexus	10.1093/pn asnexus/pg ae361
66.	<i>Lu et al.</i>	2023	Psychological Inoculation for Credibility Assessment, Sharing Intention, and Discernment of Misinformation: Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis	Journal Of Medical Internet Research	10.2196/49 255
67.	<i>Ma et al.</i>	2023	Fighting COVID-19 Misinformation through an Online Game Based on the Inoculation Theory: Analyzing the Mediating Effects of Perceived Threat and Persuasion Knowledge	International Journal Of Environmental Research And Public Health	10.3390/ijer ph2002098 0
68.	<i>Marten & Stadler</i>	2025	Building resilience against online misinformation: A teacher-led training promoting evaluation strategies among lower secondary students	Computers In Human Behavior	10.1016/j.c hb.2024.10 8548

69.	<i>Marten et al.</i>	2025	Did 5G radiation really kill birds? Training lower secondary students in epistemic strategies to counter online misinformation	Learning And Individual Differences	10.1016/j.lindif.2025.102685
70.	<i>McGrew</i>	2024	Teaching lateral reading: Interventions to help people read like fact checkers	Current Opinion In Psychology	10.1016/j.copsyc.2023.101737
71.	<i>McGrew & Chinoy</i>	2022	Fighting misinformation in college: students learn to search and evaluate online information through flexible modules	Information And Learning Science	10.1108/ILS-09-2021-0081
72.	<i>Mirhoseini et al.</i>	2023	Actively open-minded thinking is key to combating fake news: A multimethod study	Information & Management	10.1016/j.im.2023.103761
73.	<i>Modirrousta-Galian et al.</i>	2023	Effects of Inductive Learning and Gamification on News Veracity Discernment	Journal Of Experimental Psychology-Applied	10.1037/xap0000458
74.	<i>Moore & Hancock</i>	2022	A digital media literacy intervention for older adults improves resilience to fake news	Scientific Reports	10.1038/s41598-022-08437-0
75.	<i>Naderer & Oprea</i>	2021	Increasing Advertising Literacy to Unveil Disinformation in Green Advertising	Environmental Communication-A Journal Of Nature And Culture	10.1080/17524032.2021.1919171
76.	<i>Neylan et al.</i>	2023	How to “inoculate” against multimodal misinformation: A conceptual replication of Roozenbeek and van der Linden (2020)	Scientific Reports	10.1038/s41598-023-43885-2
77.	<i>Nygren & Efimova</i>	2025	Investigating the long-term impact of misinformation interventions in upper secondary education	Plos One	10.1371/journal.pone.0326928
78.	<i>Okuhara et al.</i>	2025	Effectiveness and determinants of narrative-based corrections for health misinformation: A systematic review	Patient Education And Counseling	10.1016/j.pec.2025.109253
79.	<i>Oliveira et al.</i>	2024	Confronting misinformation related to health and the environment: a systematic review	Journal Of Science Communication	10.22323/2.23010901
80.	<i>Oliveira Moreira et al.</i>	2024	JEDi - a digital educational game to support student training in identifying portuguese-written fake news: Case studies in high school, undergraduate and graduate scenarios	Education And Information Technologies	10.1007/s10639-023-12309-z
81.	<i>Ono & Ogata</i>	2025	Framework of a Disinformation Game Based on the Narrative Warfare in Russo-Ukrainian War	Journal Of Robotics, Networking And Artificial Life	10.57417/jrnal.11.1_11
82.	<i>Opgenhaffen</i>	2022	Fact-Checking Interventions on Social Media Using Cartoon Figures: Lessons Learned from the Tooties	Digital Journalism	10.1080/21670811.2021.2011758
83.	<i>Orosz et al.</i>	2023	A prosocial fake news intervention with durable effects	Scientific Reports	10.1038/s41598-023-30867-7
84.	<i>Orosz et al.</i>	2024	Strategies to combat misinformation: Enduring effects of a 15-minute online intervention on critical-thinking adolescents	Computers In Human Behavior	10.1016/j.chb.2024.108338
85.	<i>Orosz et al.</i>	2024	Softly empowering a prosocial expert in the family: lasting effects of a counter-misinformation intervention in an informational autocracy	Scientific Reports	10.1038/s41598-024-61232-x

86.	<i>Panizza et al.</i>	2022	Lateral reading and monetary incentives to spot disinformation about science	Scientific Reports	10.1038/s41598-022-09168-y
87.	<i>Paula Gil</i>	2024	Gamification as a Methodology to Enhance Analytical and Sustainable Engagement on Social Media	Discover Education	10.1007/s44217-023-00074-7
88.	<i>Peng et al.</i>	2024	The media literacy dilemma: can ChatGPT facilitate the discernment of online health misinformation?	Frontiers In Communication	10.3389/fcomm.2024.1487213
89.	<i>Pillai & Fazio</i>	2023	Explaining Why Headlines Are True or False Reduces Intentions to Share False Information	Collabra-Psychology	10.1525/collabra.87617
90.	<i>Porter et al.</i>	2024	Shoves, nudges and combating misinformation: evidence on a new approach	Behavioural Public Policy	10.1017/bpp.2024.42
91.	<i>Pretus et al.</i>	2024	The Misleading count: an identity-based intervention to counter partisan misinformation sharing	Philosophical Transactions Of The Royal Society B-Biological Sciences	10.1098/rstb.2023.0040
92.	<i>Qian et al.</i>	2023	Fighting cheapfakes: Using a digital media literacy intervention to motivate reverse search of out-of-context visual misinformation	Journal Of Computer-Mediated Communication	10.1093/jcmc/zmac024
93.	<i>Rasmussen et al.</i>	2024	Public Health Communication Reduces COVID-19 Misinformation Sharing and Boosts Self-Efficacy	Journal Of Experimental Political Science	10.1017/XPS.2024.2
94.	<i>Rau & Premo</i>	2025	Systematic Review of Educational Approaches to Misinformation	Educational Psychology Review	10.1007/s10648-025-10012-8
95.	<i>Redaelli et al.</i>	2025	Mastering critical thinking skills is strongly associated with the ability to recognize fakeness and misinformation	Frontiers In Education	10.3389/educ.2025.1577692
96.	<i>Reinhardt et al.</i>	2025	Experimental testing of active vs. passive inoculation interventions on adolescents' news discernment and learning enjoyment	Journal Of Media Psychology: Theories, Methods, And Applications	
97.	<i>Rho et al.</i>	2025	Inoculating students against misleading data visualizations with perceptual training and informative feedback	Computers & Education	10.1016/j.compedu.2025.105413
98.	<i>Roozenbeek et al.</i>	2022	Technique-based inoculation against real-world misinformation	Royal Society Open Science	10.1098/rso.s.211719
99.	<i>Roozenbeek et al.</i>	2022	Psychological inoculation improves resilience against misinformation on social media	Science Advances	10.1126/sciadv.abo6254
100.	<i>Roozenbeek et al.</i>	2021	Disentangling Item and Testing Effects in Inoculation Research on Online Misinformation: Solomon Revisited	Educational And Psychological Measurement	10.1177/0013164420940378
101.	<i>Skipper et al.</i>	2023	'But wait, that isn't real': A proof-of-concept study evaluating 'Project Real', a co-created intervention that helps young people to spot fake news online	British Journal Of Developmental Psychology	10.1111/bjdp.12456
102.	<i>Smith et al.</i>	2025	Inoculation reduces social media engagement with affectively polarized content in the UK and US.	Communications Psychology	10.1038/s44271-025-00189-7
103.	<i>Spearing et al.</i>	2025	Countering AI-generated misinformation with preemptive source discreditation and debunking	Royal Society Open Science	10.1098/rso.s.242148
104.	<i>Stein et al.</i>	2023	Realtime user ratings as a strategy for combatting misinformation: an experimental study	Scientific Reports	

105.	<i>Swire-Thompson et al.</i>	2024	Discrediting Health Disinformation Sources: Advantages of Highlighting Low Expertise	Journal Of Experimental Psychology-General	10.1037/xge0001627
106.	<i>Taerning et al.</i>	2023	A tale about facts and opinions: The impact of a drama intervention on middle-school students' information literacy	Interaction Design And Architectures	
107.	<i>Tamboer et al.</i>	2024	Do You Know What Fake News Is? An Exploration of and Intervention to Increase Youth's Fake News Literacy	Youth And Society	10.1177/0044118X231205930
108.	<i>Tang et al.</i>	2025	Effects of a News Literacy Video on News Literacy Perceptions and Misinformation Evaluation	Media And Communication	10.17645/mac.8983
109.	<i>Tay et al.</i>	2022	A comparison of prebunking and debunking interventions for implied versus explicit misinformation	British Journal Of Psychology	10.1111/bjop.12551
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